

D2.2

Co – design of joint stakeholder initiative

skillbill

SKILL TO BOOST INNOVATION & PROFESSIONAL
FULFILLMENT IN A SUSTAINABLE ECONOMY

Q-PLAN INTERNATIONAL ADVISORS PC

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ABBREVIATIONS

AB	Advisory Board
CCW	Co – creation workshop
CHP	Combined Heat and Power
CSP	Concentrated Solar Power
CV	Curriculum Vitae
DoA	Description of Action
EU	European Union
FC	Fuel Cells
GA	Grant Agreement
HVO	Hydrotreated Vegetable Oil
JSI	Joint Stakeholder Initiative
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LHE	Lighthouse Expert
MML	Mobilisation and Mutual Learning
NIMBY	“Not in my back yard” Syndrome
PV	Photovoltaics
RES	Renewable Energy Systems
SMEs	Small and Medium-sized Enterprises
Syngas	Synthesis Gas
VRE	Variable Renewable Energy
VET	Vocational & Educational Training
WG(s)	Working Group(s)
WHR	Waste Heat Recovery

Executive Summary

The present document titled “Co – design of Joint Stakeholder Initiative“, describes the approach followed to develop the framework for the establishment of a Joint Stakeholder Initiative within the context of the Horizon Europe SKILLBILL project. One of the main objectives of SKILLBILL is to develop a large and strong foundation for the acceleration of renewable energy deployment. To achieve that, SKILLBILL is establishing four interdisciplinary Working Groups (WGs) under the framework of Joint Stakeholder Initiative with key players and knowledge holders deriving from different backgrounds of the Quadruple helix within the renewable energy and advanced biofuels sector. The project aims at pushing the development of the next generation technologies in the energy sector towards sustainability and circularity by design, and to align priorities and needs in the whole value chain.

The Joint Stakeholder Initiative commenced with the initial design phase, encompassing the determination of the number and thematic focus of four different Working Groups, the establishment of a monitoring framework, the formulation of selection criteria, and the development of an operational model. Subsequently, the focus shifted to the meticulous preparation of official membership documents, including the drafting of Terms of Reference (ToRs) and the formulation of acceptance declarations. As May 2023 unfolded, active stakeholder engagement took precedence, laying the foundation for collaborative efforts. This was followed by the execution of a productive co-creation workshop in June 2023, facilitating innovative idea exchange. Presently in August 2023, the initiative stands at the stage of delivering the anticipated outcomes, fully reported in this deliverable named D2.2 “Co-design of joint stakeholder initiative”. Looking forward, the coming months of September and October 2023 are designated for the formalization of official membership of stakeholders that have already expressed their interest to join forces in the Working Groups that will constitute the Joint Stakeholder Initiative as a whole. Conclusively, the project's momentum persists as activities within WGs take center stage, starting in November 2023 and extending into subsequent phases.

More specifically, SKILLBILL is expected to develop and deploy four collaborative structures, named WGs, with different thematic focus on: i) sustainable and renewable electricity, ii) sustainable mobility, iii) sustainable and renewable heat and iv) sustainable and renewable fuels, which will involve stakeholders from across the quadruple helix (scientific community, policy makers, energy associations, industry and technology providers, SMEs and potential investors in the energy sectors). These structures, named WGs will be composed by 6-8 members, will meet in semestrial basis throughout the project's duration and will actively express their members' interests and perspectives, shaping the development of the next generation of renewable energy systems and highlighting skill gaps and education needs in several levels in the energy sector.

Prior to the official start of the Working Groups work in November 2023, a common protocol for the identification and selection of the WG members based on specific selection criteria has been developed, followed by guidelines for inviting members, for managing their inclusion along with managing potential conflicts of interest which may arise during project activities.

To successfully establish and operate the Joint Stakeholder Initiative and the four WGs as a result, SKILLBILL organised a co-creation workshop (in June 2023) addressed to WGs members, with the participation of SKILLBILL Advisory Board, and the consortium partners in order to co-elaborate a detailed operational model of the structure to ensure, beforehand, efficient forthcoming activities outcomes. The mission of SKILLBILL's Joint Stakeholder Initiative as well as the WGs specific objectives, the initial design of the operation model and the expected outcomes have been clearly defined in the context of this co-creation workshop. The rights and duties of the members, the activities in which they will be called to participate in and an indicative timeline for these activities

have been presented in detail. During the workshop, attendees were asked to express some interesting topics for discussion for the upcoming WGs semestrial meetings, with the ultimate goal to contribute towards SKILLBILL's Joint Stakeholder Initiative expected outcomes, but also keep them motivated and engaged on interesting topics of discussion.

In order to set up clear communication pathways among WGs members and their leader, the points of reference for the administrative issues and the technical issues were communicated with the members. Moreover, a management and monitoring framework along with an easy-to-use management tool, the Stakeholder Matrix, has been developed to facilitate the everyday management of the Joint Stakeholder Initiative.

During the forthcoming months and while the Joint Stakeholder Initiative will fully deploy its work, WG members will be asked to officially accept the Terms of Reference, respecting also the GDPR rules, so become official members and start working together.

1. Introduction

Aim and Scope

SKILLBILL aims at creating several paths towards increased skills with innovative learning methods, having as ultimate goal the renewable energy development acceleration. To achieve this, the project is set to greatly enhance cooperation between key players (stakeholders), using open discussion through a Joint Stakeholder Initiative, gaining access to useful insights into training needs and practices. Along these lines, for demand-driven innovation in the renewable energy sector, SKILLBILL will deliver a combination of training programmes in this sector (RES), addressed to the whole value chain of energy and tailored policy recommendations. Towards these outcomes, under the framework of SKILLBILL, an online repository has been developed named Green Portal. Moreover, a permanent education program on RES at European level will be developed along with vocational educational training.

Under the umbrella of the Joint Stakeholder Initiative, SKILLBILL will set-up four interdisciplinary **Working Groups (WGs)**. In order to kick-off the operation of the WGs, a **co-creation workshop** was foreseen (by SKILLBILL Grant Agreement) to be organised in order to co-design the operational model of the WGs as well as to identify the topics of discussion for the upcoming WG meetings. Along these lines, a dedicated **protocol for the SKILLBILL WGs members** has been co-elaborated to set out the framework as well as the approach to be followed for setting up and running these structures, ensuring the effective management of stakeholders' exchange.

The **overarching aim** of this deliverable is to describe the approach for the development of SKILLBILL's WGs and establish a common protocol that will guide the whole process of identifying, recruiting and engaging relevant energy actors in the activities of work, along with the outcomes on the WGs' operation, as they were co-created during the co-creation workshop.

Specific objectives of this report are to:

- Describe the **WG structures** that will operate in the frame of Joint Stakeholder Initiative, along with their expected outcomes, mission and the “rights and duties” of their members.
- Elaborate **guidelines** on how partners approached the selection, contact and engagement of stakeholders at a regional level, in order to create an international initiative, as well as **principles** for fostering their inclusiveness.
- Define the **main activities** in which WGs members will participate throughout the process of developing recommendations as well as the process of rolling out and replicating these recommendations at several renewable energy sectors.
- Establish a framework and tools for **managing and monitoring** the operation and the results of the WGs, with a view to appropriately keeping track and quantifying the results of the project in terms of stakeholder engagement.
- Present the **results** of the **co-creation workshop**, which kicked-off the activities of the Joint Stakeholder Initiative, along with preparatory actions needed for WGs organization.

Report outline

This report presents the framework for the WGs and the results of the co-creation workshop. It is comprised of 5 distinct chapters:

- **Chapter 1** provides introductory information about the SKILLBILL project and the context in which this report on WGs framework and approach has been elaborated.
- **Chapter 2** outlines the methodology employed to establish and activate the Joint Stakeholder Initiative. It highlights the formation of focused WGs and their operational model through a co-creation process.
- **Chapter 3** describes the objectives of SKILLBILL Joint Stakeholder Initiative and the WGs as well as the operational model of the WGs and the organisation of the co-creation workshop under the framework of SKILLBILL.
- **Chapter 4** provides the results of the co-creation workshop.
- **Chapter 5** concludes on the next steps and the forthcoming WGs activities.

Last but not least, the Annexes of this report include: an **Info pack on SKILLBILL** (Annex I) to be utilized as catalyst for attracting stakeholders, a **Registration and Informed Consent Form** (Annex II) for the co-creation workshop, an **Initial Official Invitation** (Annex III), the **WG Design** (Annex IV) describing the activities of the WG in details, the **Terms of Reference** of the WGs (Annex V); a template for the **Declaration of Acceptance** used for WGs members (Annex VI) to declare in written that they wish to be part of the Joint Stakeholder Initiative; a **Subject Form** (Annex VII) in case of membership withdrawal, an **Indicative Agenda of WG meetings** (Annex VIII), a **Reporting Template for WG Meetings** (Annex IX), the **WG Members Matrix** (Annex X) which will be used by the Working Group Manager to monitor the engagement of stakeholders in the WGs, the **Agenda** of the co-creation Workshop (Annex XI), **Photos** of the co-creation workshop (Annex XII), the **Presentation** of the co-creation workshop (XIII) and finally the **Social Media Posts** (Annex XIV).

2. Methodology

The successful execution of any multifaceted project necessitates a **collaborative approach** that brings together diverse perspectives, expertise, and resources. In line with this principle, SKILLBILL's initiative adopts a joint stakeholder methodology that fosters collective engagement, shared decision-making, and effective resource allocation. This methodology represents a structured framework through which various stakeholders, each contributing their unique insights and capacities, collaborate to achieve common objectives. The Joint Stakeholder Initiative is orchestrated with a well-defined **mission** and specific **objectives** in mind. The methodological approach is structured to ensure the alignment of stakeholders, resources, and strategies towards the achievement of these **targeted goals**. The initial phase of a Joint Stakeholder Initiative involves the comprehensive **identification and classification of key stakeholders**. This process is driven by the recognition that a holistic understanding of the project's ecosystem is crucial for its ultimate success. Stakeholders are classified based on their roles, interests, and potential impacts on the initiative. This step ensures that all pertinent parties, including governmental bodies, industry representatives, community organizations and experts, are included in the collaborative process.

Once stakeholders are identified, the initiative employs tailored **engagement strategies** to involve them effectively throughout the project lifecycle. The engagement strategies encompass networks of consortium, personal contacts, and comprehensive communication pack. This **communication pack** contains project details, initiative specifics, e-mail templates, and informative files, guiding stakeholders on their roles and expectations as members.

According to the literature, “stakeholder mapping” is a support tool for the analysis of the stakeholder community and a tool for supporting the decision-making processes of managers. There are different methods, matrixes, grids and maps that utilize different characteristics to map the stakeholder community e.g., influence, attitude, power, interest, support and legitimacy¹²³⁴.

It is clear that energy stakeholder groups have different profiles and so their engagement in SKILLBILL project activities should be different. For mapping purposes, the approaches of Bryson¹, and Ackermann, Eden and Brown⁵ were used. These authors evaluated two characteristics, **power** and **interest**, to create a Power vs Interest grid (matrix) and categorize stakeholders based on their power or influence and interest in the project. Both characteristics were rated on a scale of Low or High and assessed by consortium partners. Based on the stakeholder Power vs Interest matrix (Figure 1), the stakeholders were divided into four basic groups and each of these groups includes those who should be:

1 BRYSON J. M., 2011. *Strategic Planning for Public and Nonprofit Organizations: A Guide to Strengthening and Sustaining Organizational Achievement*. San Francisco: John Wiley & Sons. ISBN: 978-0-470-39251-5

2 MITCHELL, R.K., B.R. AGLE and D. J WOOD, 1997. Toward a Theory of Stakeholder Identification and Salience: Defining the Principle of Who and What Really Counts. *Academy of Management Review*; 22(4), 853–886. ISSN 0363-7425

3 OLANDER, S., A. LANDIN, 2005. Evaluation of stakeholder influence in the implementation of construction projects. *International Journal of Project Management*; 23(4), 321-328. ISSN 0263-7863

4 CHINYIO, E. et al., 2010: *Construction Stakeholder Management*. Chichester (United Kingdom): Blackwell Publishing. ISBN 978-1-4051-8098-6

5 ACKERMANN, F., C. EDEN and I. BROWN, 2004. *The Practice of Making Strategy: A Step-by Step Guide*. London: Sage Publications. ISBN 978-0761944942

- Monitored
- Kept Informed
- Kept Satisfied
- Managed closely

The figure below explains the different approaches, that are already implemented for the initial engagement and will be followed for the future communications for the segregated stakeholders under the framework of SKILLBILL:

Figure 1. Stakeholder Power/Influence vs Interest Matrix

Low power - Low interest: WG Manager should monitor these people, and make sure they are not demotivated or overburdened with excessive communication.

Low power – High interest: WG Manager should keep these people adequately informed and talk to them to ensure that no major issues are arising.(eg. Research & Academia)

High power - Low Interest: these stakeholders, even if they have no interest in the topic, must be kept informed and their needs must be taken into account because they wield power. This type of stakeholders should be treated with caution as they may use their power in the project in undesirable ways if they are dissatisfied.

High power - High interest: these are decision-makers and have the biggest impact on the WG’s success and hence WG Manager must work closely with these stakeholders to manage their expectations (eg.on policy, decision making) and to ensure that they agree with and support the activities of the Project.

The engagement of stakeholders follows a well-defined **selection process** guided by **specific criteria**. Stakeholders are identified based on their expertise, relevance, and potential impact on the Joint Stakeholder Initiative. The selection process involves a comprehensive assessment of individuals and organizations within the project's ecosystem, ensuring representation across diverse sectors. Stakeholders who demonstrate a vested interest, aligned values, and the potential to contribute meaningfully are prioritized. This approach guarantees that the engaged stakeholders possess a collective proficiency and a shared commitment to the initiative's objectives, enriching the collaborative environment and maximizing the potential for successful outcomes.

An initiative of experts should consider **separating the experts in WGs** for various compelling reasons. Firstly, by dividing the experts into smaller specialized teams, the initiative can capitalize on individual strengths and expertise, maximizing efficiency and productivity. Each group can focus on a specific sector of the renewables, leading to in-depth analysis and comprehensive solutions. Moreover, WGs enable a diverse range of perspectives, fostering innovative ideas and creative problem-solving. Collaboration within smaller teams can lead to more engaged discussions, as experts can actively contribute and brainstorm ideas. Additionally, WGs facilitate efficient resource allocation, ensuring that tasks are distributed evenly and completed in a timely manner. This approach also allows better organization and coordination, as each team can be assigned specific responsibilities and outcomes. Overall, separating experts into WGs promotes synergy, collaboration, and a holistic approach, enhancing the initiative's overall success and achieving desired outcomes.

Central to the methodology is the establishment of WGs, each operating under a defined **operational model**. This operational model outlines the framework within which the WGs function, including guidelines for communication protocols, responsibilities, and collaboration mechanisms. Regular meetings serve as pivotal points for interaction, fostering dialogue, sharing of insights, and collective decision-making. The operational model also delineates the rights, duties, and benefits of WG membership, ensuring a harmonized approach to engagement. Operationalizing the collaborative efforts within the Joint Stakeholder Initiative, the methodology incorporates a structured framework to guide the functioning of the designated WGs. These WGs, formed as a result of the co-creation workshop, serve as the nuclei of focused collaboration, facilitating the efficient pursuit of specific objectives within the initiative. Each WG operates within a tailored framework that defines its scope, responsibilities, decision-making processes, and engagement mechanisms. This framework ensures clarity of purpose and accountability, as well as a harmonious integration of the WG's efforts with the broader initiative. Regular communication channels, including scheduled meetings, virtual platforms, and data-sharing repositories, are established to foster ongoing information exchange and collaboration. The methodology promotes a participatory ethos, where WG members, drawn from diverse stakeholder segments, contribute their specialized expertise and insights. Additionally, the framework incorporates feedback loops and periodic reviews, enabling iterative refinement of strategies and alignment with evolving project dynamics. By placing the WGs within a defined operational framework, the Joint Stakeholder Initiative gains the advantage of targeted and coordinated actions, driving the attainment of specific objectives while maintaining a cohesive alignment with the overarching mission.

A pivotal consideration revolves around the meticulous **management** of the WGs within the Joint Stakeholder Initiative. Recognizing the multifaceted nature of the initiative, an adept approach is adopted where technical expertise and administrative acumen are intertwined to ensure seamless functioning. WGs are overseen by individuals possessing technical backgrounds, capable of navigating intricate technical discussions and providing informed insights. Simultaneously, administrative roles are designated to individuals adept at streamlining logistics, managing documentation, and orchestrating cohesive communication within and between the WGs. This dual-

pronged management approach is pivotal in fostering an environment where technical excellence converges with administrative efficiency, ultimately enhancing the WGs' ability to collaboratively address complex challenges and execute the initiative's objectives with precision.

The formulation of smaller stakeholder groups within the overarching Joint Stakeholder Initiative necessitates a collaborative and inclusive approach that respects the diverse perspectives and expertise of participants. To achieve this, a **co-creation workshop** methodology encourages active engagement, collective brainstorming, and the emergence of well-defined smaller stakeholder clusters. The following outlines the steps and principles guiding a co-creation workshop:

Prior to the workshop, a preparatory phase is initiated to ensure the effective execution of the co-creation process. This includes identifying potential stakeholders, mapping their expertise, interests, and concerns, and segmenting them based on commonalities. Stakeholders representing a spectrum of perspectives and interests are invited to participate in the co-creation workshop. Invitations are extended to individuals who possess domain-specific knowledge, community representatives, industry experts, and other relevant stakeholders. The inclusivity of the participants contributes to a well-rounded and comprehensive formulation of smaller groups, a phase which is closely connected and could be combined with the initial identification and engaging activities as described in previous paragraphs. The organizer of the workshop is tasked with the preparation of all the needed material for the workshop including presentations, ice-breakers, and co-creation sessions along with the design of needed tools, e.g. Miro, Mentimeter, etc. Additionally, facilitators and moderators are selected to guide the workshop discussions and activities, ensuring a structured and productive environment. An important step prior to the workshop is the dissemination of the event to attract more stakeholders.

At the onset of the workshop, facilitators provide an overview of the Joint Stakeholder Initiative's objectives, emphasizing the significance of formulating smaller groups. Participants are encouraged to recognize the value of their individual contributions in shaping the initiative's outcomes and addressing specific challenges within their respective domains. The core of the co-creation workshop involves interactive sessions designed to generate ideas and cluster stakeholders into smaller groups. Participants engage in facilitated brainstorming activities, sharing their insights, perspectives, and visions for the initiative. Through guided discussions, common themes and interests emerge, forming the basis for the creation of smaller stakeholder clusters. Based on the outcomes of the idea generation sessions, participants collaborate to define and refine the characteristics of each smaller stakeholder group. This includes determining the scope, objectives, and shared goals of each subgroup. Facilitators help guide these discussions, ensuring that the resulting group definitions are coherent, relevant, and aligned with the initiative's overarching objectives.

Finally the the co-creation workshop concludes with the **documentation** of the formulated smaller stakeholder groups, including their objectives, scope, and member composition. Participants are invited to express their commitment to the selected groups and their willingness to actively engage in subsequent collaborative activities.

3. Implementation under the framework of SKILLBILL

3.1 Activation of Joint Stakeholder Initiative

Mission

Joint Stakeholder Initiative under the framework of SKILLBILL is a pan-european network of stakeholders coming across the entire value chain of renewable energy and sustainable biofuels sector. It also includes researchers, policy makers and groups representing potential investors. The Joint Stakeholder Initiative operates as an exchange structure for various stakeholders and experts to share their knowledge and input with their expertise to the implementation of SKILLBILL.

Objectives

The objectives of SKILLBILL's Joint Stakeholder Initiative embody a commitment to interdisciplinarity and the quadruple helix approach, uniting academia, industry, government, and society as described in the previous chapter. The primary goal is to spearhead the development of the renewable energy technologies next generation. Through collaborative efforts, the initiative aims to address the priorities and needs of the entire value chain within the energy sector. By fostering innovation, research, and knowledge exchange, the initiative seeks to accelerate the implementation of sustainable energy solutions. Emphasis is placed on creating a seamless integration of cutting-edge technologies, ensuring environmental sustainability, and enhancing energy efficiency. By leveraging the expertise and perspectives of diverse stakeholders, this joint initiative aims to drive transformative advancements in renewable energy, paving the way for a greener and more resilient future.

Engagement Activities

The initial recruitment of members for the WGs was implemented with the support of the SKILLBILL partners that reached out to their networks of relevant stakeholders in the field of renewables and the energy value chain. To be more specific the following table presents the profile of potential stakeholders, reflecting on the initial mapping which took place in T2.1 "Stakeholder Community mapping and user research to better appreciate current training needs and skilling practises"

Table 1. Stakeholder categories

Category	Sub – category
Scientific Community	Educational Institutions
	Researchers & Research Organisations
	Professors – Educational staff
	Administrative staff

Category	Sub – category
	Students R&D units in private companies Experts on the field
Policy Makers	EU institutions (European Commission) National and Local Public Authorities International Policy Makers Experts on International Climate, Environment and Energy Affairs, Experts on Energy Legal Affairs Crisis Managers and Energy officers Energy Market and Statistics analysts
Energy Associations	National Energy Associations Bioenergy Associations Energy Communities Energy Clusters Experts on Green Finance and Sustainable Economy, Energy Efficiency and Heat Funding Instruments
Industry Technology Providers	Hydropower Industry Solar Power Industry Wind Energy Industry Geothermal Energy Industry Biomass Energy Industry Hydrogen Industry R&D specialists Developers Energy Management Systems Solution Providers Energy Industry standardisation internal / external auditors
SMEs	RES Experts RES Engineers Workers Technicians

Category	Sub – category
	RES designers – Planners Installers - Manufacturers
Potential Investors	Investors active in the fields of energy Network operators and distributors Green Financing Providers Business Angels Venture Capitalists

In the framework of SKILLBILL, and of the four WGs in different renewable energy and sustainable biofuels sectors, which comprised of key regional stakeholders across the quadruple helix, several stakeholders were engaged including scientific community, policy makers, energy associations, industry and technology providers, SMEs and potential investors. In order to find the key players from each stakeholder group, an extensive mapping of relevant stakeholders in each focal region has taken place in T2.1 “Stakeholder community mapping and user research to better appreciate current training needs and skilling practices”. Findings fuelled the identification and selection of the key ones.

Under the T2.2 “Co-design of stakeholder joint initiative” all partners were asked to identify, engage, and select actors throughout the whole renewable energy and sustainable biofuels sector to become official members of the WGs, ones already identified under the T2.1 and of course other stakeholder that may be identified. To reach out and engage the stakeholders, Q-PLAN INTERNATIONAL PC has prepared and shared a communication pack. Consortium partners contacted possible actors in the sector through their networks and informed them about their involvement, if that falls under their interests, inviting them to the CCW that was organized under the same task.

Figure 2. Engagement Process

The following table outlines the guidelines for partners to establish the contact with stakeholders as well as principles for fostering their inclusion and effective engagement. The first contact with WG members and their invitation to join the WGs were implemented through dedicated communication materials developed by Q-PLAN to facilitate the initial approach. To engage the Stakeholders in the different WGs, the following steps were and will be followed:

Table 2. Steps for stakeholder engagement

Step	Who	Material	When
Identification and communication with potential members	Consortium Partners	Communication pack: Incl. info for SKILLBILL, SKILLBILL leaflet, online registration form for the co-creation workshop ⁶	May 2023
Co-creation Workshop	Q-PLAN	Boards prepared on Miro, or other user-friendly co-creation software	June 2023
Official Invitation to potential members that have already expressed their initial interest	Q-PLAN	ToR, Declaration of Acceptance in electronic format (e.g. Google form), Subject Form	September 2023
Official Invitation to potential members that are identified by partners, but have not yet expressed their interest	Consortium Partners	Official Invitation, ToR, Declaration of Acceptance in electronic format (e.g. Google form), Subject Form	September 2023
Acceptance of engagement	Members of WG	Officially sign a Declaration of Acceptance	September 2023 & October 2023

Although members of the WGs may be invited because of their affiliations with key organizations, they serve in their **individual capacity** to represent the interests and views of their stakeholder communities. Members of the WGs may not delegate another person to carry out the role expected from them or be replaced by any other person in all WGs activities (meetings).

3.2 Guidelines for Contact

This section outlines a set of contact guidelines for the initial and subsequent communications of partners with members of the WGs to ensure effective collaboration with them during the project.

⁶ All the relevant files are annexed at the end of this report

Dedicated communication material has been prepared to facilitate the first contact of partners with WGs members, inviting them to participate to the CCW and be official members of the WGs and to ensure that stakeholders have sufficient information concerning their participation and role in SKILLBILL WGs and their activities. In particular, the following documents have been produced:

Table 3. Communication Material with WG members

Name of the file	Description	From To	When
WG Design	A guide to the WG operation so that WG members get knowledge about the operational model	WG Manager Partners	Initial Stage
Intro to SKILLBILL	Information about SKILLBILL and WGs at a glance	Partners Possible WG members	Initial Stage
Official Invitation letter from partners	An invitation to accompany the initial communication of consortium partners with selected stakeholders	Partners Possible WG Members	Initial Stage
Registration Form including an Informed Consent form	A form to be signed by invited stakeholders evidencing the fact that they are well informed on the processing of their personal data for the needs of specific project activities and they give their consent	Partners Possible WG Members	Initial Stage
Terms of Reference	A document providing meaningful information about SKILLBILL and the activities in which members of WGs are expected to be involved, as well as their expected contribution and conditions pertaining to their membership	WG Manager or Partners WG Members	Second Stage
Declaration of Acceptance	A declaration to be signed by the invited stakeholders evidencing the fact that they agree with the terms and conditions pertaining to their participation in the respective WG, as well as that they are in fact a willing member in this multi-actor structure	WG Manager or Partners WG Members	Second Stage
Informed Consent form	A template form to be signed by invited stakeholders evidencing the fact that they are informed and give their consent to the processing of their personal data for the needs of specific project activities	WG Manager or Partners WG Members	Second Stage

Name of the file	Description	From To	When
Official invitation letter from the WG Manager	An Invitation to accompany the second communication of consortium partners with selected stakeholders	WG Manager or Partners WG Members	Second Stage

The abovementioned material has been (during initial communication) and will be (during the second stage communication for potential members) provided to prospective members of the WGs following a guiding e-mail with instructions for initial contact and subsequent communications among partners of the consortium and WGs members at different stages of the WGs framework operation. The set of guidelines for the initial contact is described below in steps and refers to the initial communication inviting potential members to the co-creation workshop, or directly inviting them as experts to the WGs of their interest.

Initial Stage: Initial Contact before co-creation workshop

- The initial contact with prospective members of each WG should be **carried out by the consortium partners**.
- **All initial contacts should be accompanied by the communication pack** prepared to this end (Official invitation letter, Info Pack, Registration Form incorporating Informed Consent form for the participation to the co-creation workshop, SKILLBILL leaflet).
- **Communication activities should employ a language that is easily understood** by the stakeholders and ensures that they comprehend their rights and duties implied by their future participation in WGs.
- **Further communication via e-mail or teleconference** is encouraged in order to reply to any questions or provide clarifications.
- Stakeholders who accept to join a WG, should be requested to sign the Declaration of Acceptance & the Informed Consent form.

Second Stage: Subsequent communications after the co-creation workshop

- As in the initial stage, the contact should be accompanied by the WG communication pack prepared to this end (Terms of Reference, Declaration of Acceptance, Informed Consent form, official invitation letter).
- Q-PLAN managing the WGs, will manage/liaise all communications with members of these structures, who have already expressed their interest. For future potential members that are to be identified after the co-creation workshop and before the official launch of the WGs, the same procedures will be followed by the partners, respecting the GDPR rules.
- WG Managers can authorise other consortium partners (e.g., Lighthouse Experts) to contact these persons only if necessary and will be kept informed during the whole communication process.
- WGs members should be properly and timely informed to participate in upcoming project activities (e.g., meetings, MMLs).

- WG Manager should ensure that no member is overloaded with information about any task at hand.
- Prior to contacting members for a specific action, necessary material and briefings should be prepared to inform participants about the scope of the activity and their expected role.

Selection Process and Selection Criteria

Consortium partners were responsible for the initial selection of stakeholders to be included in the WG set-up. The stakeholders were contacts deriving from their existing networks either identified under the T2.1 “Stakeholder community mapping and user research to better appreciate current training needs and skilling practises”, or new contacts interested on the SKILLBILL project. As mentioned before, some WG members are already identified prior to the co-creation workshop held in June 2023, and some more will be recruited by September 2023. It is important to identify the most appropriate persons based on specific criteria and expertise. A common process was followed in the initial contact (to be also followed in subsequent recruiting). The process is presented in clear steps in the figure below:

Figure 3. Selection Process

The criteria applied for selecting the members of the WGs, in line with the mission and expected structure of each WG, capture a broad range of dimensions regarding the characteristics of stakeholders necessary for their meaningful participation in WG activities. Along these lines, the following table summarises the selection criteria and justification for WG members inclusion.

Table 4: Selection criteria and inclusion rationale

No.	Selection criterion	Rationale
1	Expertise	The potential WGs' members should have expertise in the thematic of each focus group, focusing in renewable energy sector and education in techs fields and/or environment.
2	Interest	Stakeholders with high interest in the energy sector and particularly in renewable energy systems will ensure that they are driven to participate and help the project produce meaningful results with significant added value for RES users.
3	Availability	Stakeholders that have the available time required to participate will enable partners to smoothly organise and execute project activities with higher participation rates that will result in higher targets reached.
4	Relevance	The relevance of stakeholders to the project's scope and objectives is necessary to keep activities of the WG focused and to ensure that WG members can effectively contribute to the production of accordingly relevant project outputs.
5	Appropriateness	The consortium will make sure that members selected to participate in the WG are appropriate to their scope thus avoiding conflicts of interest or subjecting them in activities that may cause unnecessary inconvenience.
6	Representativeness	A balanced representation of perspectives within and across stakeholder groups is key for the WGs to collect the representative insights required to inform design, development and fine-tuning of training needs.
7	Willingness	Motivated stakeholders willing to contribute with their knowledge and experience will promote success of WG activities and will be more prone to help disseminate the project's tools and knowledge, facilitating exploitation and sustainability.
8	Gender	The recruitment of each WG will seek to keep a gender balance.

The following table presents an indicative overview of key potential interests and conflicts of key stakeholder groups of SKILLBILL that may arise during their engagement in the project, along with a set of proposed principles on how to effectively manage their engagement.

Table 5. Main interests, conflicts and engagement principles for WG members

Stakeholder Groups	Potential interests that may arise during their engagement	Conflicts that may arise during their engagement	Principles for managing their engagement
Scientific Community	Advancing research and development in renewable energy technologies.	Differences in research findings and methodologies may lead to disagreements on the best course of action.	Encourage open dialogue and collaboration between researchers and stakeholders. Ensure transparent communication of research

Stakeholder Groups	Potential interests that may arise during their engagement	Conflicts that may arise during their engagement	Principles for managing their engagement
	<p>Promoting evidence-based policies and regulations for sustainable energy.</p> <p>Ensuring environmental and social considerations are integrated into energy projects.</p> <p>Encouraging innovation and technological advancements in the energy sector.</p>	<p>Funding and resource constraints might create competition for research grants and projects.</p> <p>Tensions between academia and industry regarding the commercialization of scientific discoveries.</p>	<p>findings and methodologies.</p> <p>Foster an environment that supports interdisciplinary research and knowledge sharing</p>
Policy Makers	<p>Formulating energy policies that align with environmental goals and energy security.</p> <p>Promoting regulatory frameworks that support the integration of renewable energy sources.</p> <p>Addressing energy affordability and accessibility for the public.</p> <p>Stimulating economic growth through the energy sector.</p>	<p>Differing political ideologies might lead to disagreements on the prioritization of certain energy sources.</p> <p>Balancing short-term political objectives with long-term sustainability goals can be challenging.</p> <p>Policy decisions may face resistance from vested interests and lobbying efforts.</p>	<p>Encourage evidence-based decision-making and policy formulation.</p> <p>Engage in multi-stakeholder consultations to understand diverse perspectives.</p> <p>Seek long-term sustainable solutions over short-term political gains.</p>
Energy Associations	<p>Representing the interests of energy companies and promoting their growth.</p> <p>Advocating for favorable energy policies and regulatory frameworks.</p> <p>Facilitating knowledge exchange and collaboration among industry players.</p>	<p>Different energy associations may have conflicting priorities and interests.</p> <p>Balancing the interests of large energy corporations and smaller players (SMEs) can be challenging.</p> <p>Disagreements on the level of government intervention and regulation in the energy market.</p>	<p>Foster open dialogue and trust among stakeholder and define common objectives to align conflicting interests effectively.</p> <p>Third-party facilitators guide productive discussions and conflict resolution.</p> <p>Seek solution benefiting all parties involved</p>
Industry & Technology Providers	<p>Promoting the adoption of their energy products and services.</p> <p>Advocating for supportive policies and incentives for renewable energy technologies.</p>	<p>Competition between different technology providers may hinder cooperation.</p> <p>Balancing commercial interests with broader</p>	<p>Encourage innovation and technology-sharing for collective advancement.</p> <p>Strive for fair competition while acknowledging common goals in sustainability.</p>

Stakeholder Groups	Potential interests that may arise during their engagement	Conflicts that may arise during their engagement	Principles for managing their engagement
	Collaborating with other stakeholders to address industry challenges.	societal and environmental goals. Intellectual property disputes and concerns over technology sharing	Facilitate partnerships and collaborations among technology providers
SMEs	Accessing funding and resources to develop and implement energy projects. Participating in policy discussions to ensure their needs are considered. Identifying business opportunities in the evolving energy landscape.	Limited resources and capacity may restrict their participation in WGs. Balancing the interests of SMEs with those of larger industry players. Potential competition for funding and contracts with larger companies.	Foster an inclusive environment where SMEs have equal opportunities to contribute. Encourage partnerships between SMEs and larger entities for mutual benefit. Support capacity-building initiatives to enhance SMEs' participation.
Potential Investors	Foster an inclusive environment where SMEs have equal opportunities to contribute. Encourage partnerships between SMEs and larger entities for mutual benefit. Support capacity-building initiatives to enhance SMEs' participation.	Foster an inclusive environment where SMEs have equal opportunities to contribute. Encourage partnerships between SMEs and larger entities for mutual benefit. Support capacity-building initiatives to enhance SMEs' participation.	Foster an inclusive environment where SMEs have equal opportunities to contribute. Encourage partnerships between SMEs and larger entities for mutual benefit. Support capacity-building initiatives to enhance SMEs' participation.

Guiding principles for inclusion

The WGs guidelines introduce specific principles to ensure the effective inclusion of the diverse identified stakeholder groups in the different activities of SKILLBILL, while also facilitating gender balance and geographical representation to the degree possible within the framework of the project. Below, the principles to be followed by project partners are laid out, referring to inclusion, geographical representation and gender aspects.

Table 6: Guiding principles for stakeholder inclusion in project activities

Category	Guiding principles
Inclusion	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Ensure participation in project activities from the full range of potentially interested stakeholders spanning across the entire range of the key stakeholder groups identified.

Category	Guiding principles
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Timely identify any potential barriers to the participation of the interested stakeholders in the activities of the project (such as accessibility, lack of awareness). • Assess and determine effective means of surpassing potential barriers to participation (such as broad and targeted information sharing via online means and other suitable channels, etc.). • Appropriately take into account the needs, interests and potential conflicts that may arise among the targeted stakeholder groups in the framework of their participation in the activities of the project.
Regional Geographical Representation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ensure a various representation of different stakeholders within pan European level and if possible international • Address and engage with stakeholders within the pan-European and international level of the project, based on the access of partners to relevant networks, platforms and initiatives.
Gender aspects	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ensure that people from all gender spectrums have equal opportunities and access to participate in project activities, from formulating policy recommendations to identifying skills gaps and needs in the energy sector • Uphold ethical communication standards by respecting human dignity and proactively eradicate any traces of gender-related bias and within the project's communication campaigns. • Engage in constructive discussions with stakeholders throughout SKILLBILL activities and implement the commitment to gender balance (e.g. equal participation, ensuring that all views are heard, motivating women to participate equally in discussions).^{7, 8}

3.3 Operational Model

Working Groups Categorization

In the process of forming the four WGs, the consortium partnership played a crucial role through a collaborative voting process. During the 2nd semestrial SKILLBILL project meeting (Helsinki, Finland, February 7th & 8th 2023), some partners proposed potential categories for the WGs, driven from their unique expertise and interests. Through a democratic voting system, members cast their ballots, ranking the proposed categories based on relevance and priority. The categories with the highest number of votes were established as the foundation for the WGs. This inclusive approach ensured that the WGs' thematics were aligned closely with the consortium's shared objectives and also allowed the incorporation of diverse perspectives. The formation of these four WGs, driven by the

⁷ <https://www.catalyst.org/research/workplace-inclusion-covid-19/>

⁸ <https://www.nature.com/articles/d41586-023-01467-2>

collective input of the consortium partnership, set the stage for effective collaboration and co-creation, as experts from different backgrounds came together to address challenges and pursue opportunities within their respective categories.

The consortium had to choose from the following sets of WG division categories

The 1st Approach: was **similar to the Grant Agreement (GA)**, but moving the hydrogen in the fourth category/fourth WG with Fuel Cells and storage, as the most Fuel Cells operate with Hydrogen (H₂):

- Solar (thermal and electrical)
- Biofuels (biomethane, Biodiesel, Bioethanol) and Biomass Combustion Systems (Combustion and Gasification)
- Wind Energy
- Hydrogen, Fuel Cells and Storage

The 2nd Approach: was based on [IRENA: Renewable Energy and Jobs](#) and the global renewable energy employment (acknowledging that these RES employ most personnel worldwide)

- Solar
- Biofuels
- Hydropower
- Wind Energy

The 3rd Approach: was a proposition of a partner during the meeting for RES categorisation.

- Dispatchable (incl. geothermal & Waste heat recovery)
- Renewable Fuels and Energy Vector
- Variable RES (incl. wind and PV)
- Other RES technologies

The 4th Approach: followed the Master sessions and categorisation, focusing on the end use of energy

- Fuels
- Heat
- Electricity
- Mobility

To come to a conclusion and to follow a democratic procedure, partners had to study the positive and negative side of each one of the approaches.

Table 7. Advantages and disadvantages of each approach for the selection of WG categories

	Pros	Cons
1 st approach	Based on GA	Does not include Hydropower, which is the 2 nd largest renewable electricity source in EU (source),

	Pros	Cons
2 nd approach	Based on global renewable energy employment Includes Hydropower, the 2 nd largest renewable energy source	Does not follow GA Does not include H ₂ , FC and storage
3 rd approach	Includes all the RES categories	Difficult to find LHE, with expertise in a lot of categories More complicated for the recommendations needed
4 th approach	Follows the Master	Maybe difficult to find LHE, in master’s categories More complicated for the recommendations needed

The figure below represents the outcomes of the voting process conducted within the consortium partnership using a pie chart. The chart illustrates the distribution of votes across the various categories proposed for the formation of the four WGs. Each category is represented as a separate slice of the pie, with the size of each slice corresponding to the proportion of votes received. The chart provides a clear visual snapshot of the relative popularity of each category, with larger slices indicating higher levels of support. This pie chart offers a comprehensive overview of the consortium's collective preferences and highlights the themes that garnered the most significant interest. The clarity of the figure enabled the consortium members to quickly identify the chosen categories, guiding the subsequent collaborative efforts of the WGs to address the identified challenges and opportunities effectively.

Figure 4. Results of the voting for the working group categories

As a result, the WGs have been established in four (4) sub-sectors following the Master Segmentation in pan-european level, with diverse profiles of renewable and sustainable energy-related context (energy sources, value chains, policy framework) as well as attributes, needs, perceptions and socio-economic context. Each WG focuses on bringing together key regional players and knowledge holders with diverse backgrounds, expertise, and interests, supporting them to collaborate, explore opportunities and co-create innovative solutions and policy frameworks.

Number and Thematic focus of Working Groups

Having acknowledged the 4th approach as the most interesting, partners decided on the WGs context. The table below presents a clear and concise overview of the thematic focuses of each WG in the energy sector. Each row represents an individual WG, and the columns showcase the distinct thematic areas they are dedicated to addressing. The table allows easy comparison and understanding of the different focuses, facilitating efficient decision-making and coordination. The thematic categories are well-defined, enabling WG members to identify their specific interests and align with the most relevant WG. This organized and visually accessible presentation ensures that all stakeholders are well-informed about the objectives and expertise of each WG, fostering effective collaboration and collective progress towards achieving the initiative’s overarching goals.

Table 8. Thematic Focus of Working Groups

Icon	Thematic Focus	Technologies
	Sustainable and Renewable Electricity & Skills Gap impacting its full deployment potential	Power to grid and market of electricity: characteristics of power grid, variability of energy mix, operation of electricity market, incentive to promote the installation of renewable energy technologies for power generation. VRE ⁹ technologies: PV ¹⁰ systems (small and large scale), wind turbines, interaction with the grid Dispatchable Renewable Energy Technologies: Hydroelectric, CSP ¹¹ , linear collectors, geothermal and WHR ⁴ , Organic Rankine Cycle
	Sustainable Mobility & Skills Gap impacting its full deployment potential	Road Transport: Fuels and emissions of road vehicles (light and heavy), electric vehicles, hydrogen cars, biofuels (generation and distribution and storage), fast chargers for electric vehicles

⁹ VRE: Variable Renewable Energy

¹⁰ PV: Photovoltaic

¹¹ CSP: Concentrated Solar Power

Icon	Thematic Focus	Technologies
		<p>Air transport: Sustainable Aviation fuels, Hydrogen aircraft, Electric Aircraft</p> <p>Maritime transport: carbon footprint of maritime transportation, sustainable marine fuels</p>
	<p>Sustainable and Renewable Heat & Skills Gap impacting its full deployment potential</p>	<p>Renewable heat technologies: geothermal, bioenergy (incl. CHP¹²), WHR¹³, electrical heating and district heating</p> <p>Sustainable heat in built environment: Insulation, heat pumps, solar energy, wood pellet, district heating and heat storage</p> <p>Industrial renewable heat</p>
	<p>Sustainable and Renewable Fuels & Skills Gap impacting its full deployment potential</p>	<p>Biofuels processes (gasification, syngas¹⁴, biooils / upgrading, biomass production and pre-treatment)</p> <p>Waste to Fuels, waste oils, HVO¹⁵, pyrolysis of biomass / gasification, biowaste to biogas</p> <p>Renewable energy to chemicals and fuels (power to hydrogen, methane, ammonia, syngas process)</p>

Aim and expected outcomes of the Working Groups

The aim of the WGs is to provide knowledge and expertise on key developments and challenges that threaten the effective decarbonization of the energy sector and the deployment of renewable energy innovations. In this context, the 4 SKILLBILL WGs are designed to engage with stakeholders who address skill gaps and labor market shortages; and develop concrete solutions and actions that raise awareness and the level of education among academia, industry, decision-makers and civil

¹² CHP: Combined Heat and Power

¹³ WHR: Waste Heat Recovery

¹⁴ Syngas: Synthesis gas, is a mixture of hydrogen and carbon monoxide

¹⁵ HVO: Hydrotreated Vegetable Oil

society. Other than that SKILLBILL WGs are tasked to improve skills required to foster future-proof labor markets, in University education and research, as well as in innovation and the formulation of better policies and regulation that emphasizes, amongst others, bridging the gender gap.

To this end, each group will comprise an interdisciplinary team, including experts that can help translate technological advances into new education/training needs. As such, the outputs of each group will encompass:

- (i) **solutions** for driving the development of skills that will help implement sustainable renewable energy and fuel techs;
- (ii) meaningful **recommendations** for changes in regulation that shape a favorable environment for actors driving the energy transition towards net-zero.
- (iii) **guidelines** for education / training programs to facilitate skilling, reskilling and upskilling.

The horizontal theme of all four WGs is the **identification of new jobs** for renewable energy and fuel technologies existing and next generations as well as **skills required** for these jobs.

The **goals of the WGs** are:

- (i) to inform industries on future needs to drive the RES development,
- (ii) provide suggestions to policy makers on how to improve the regulatory frameworks,
- (iii) to translate the technological advances into new education / training needs.

To fulfil their role, it is envisaged that each WG will operate through semestrial online meetings, that will be facilitated by a Lighthouse Expert. The online meetings will also use digital means (miro, online questionnaires, online forms etc,) to capture the members' ideas, suggestions and priorities. To animate each WG in a direct and structured exchange of ideas, a common chat is encouraged to be created, to share information and views on the targeted thematic.

3.4 Rights and Duties of Working Group Members

The following table summarises the rights and duties of stakeholders participating in WGs, as provided in the respective Terms of Reference and Declaration of Acceptance.

Table 9: Rights and duties of WGs members

Rights	Duties
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Stakeholders participate in WGs voluntarily and have the right to withdraw at any time or refuse participation without facing any adverse consequences. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Stakeholders agree to abide by the Terms of Reference which explain in further detail expected involvement as well as terms pertaining to their membership.
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Stakeholders' have the right to preserve their anonymity in project's activities, other than the WGs' activities, to which they will be involved in and in reports or publications produced. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Stakeholders participate in their individual capacity and not delegate any expected work to another person without prior written agreement.
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Stakeholders have the right to request further processing and storage of their data 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Stakeholders ensure that they are involved in project activities in complete

<p>by the consortium to be ceased without having to justify their request.</p>	<p>independence and there is no conflict of interest affecting their participation.</p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Stakeholders have the right to access project results, as testers, ahead of their public release in order to provide input for fine-tuning them in alignment with the needs of their users, given the consent on results access by partners 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Stakeholders must not disclose any information provided to them in the frame of SKILLBILL activities and fully respect all confidentiality requirements.
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Stakeholders reserve the right to receive remuneration, subject to fulfilment of specific conditions outlined Section 3.7, ensuring equitable compensation for their contributions within the established parameters. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Stakeholders have to actively participate in SKILLBILL WGs’ activities (semestrial meetings).

3.5 Timeplan of scheduled activities

The table below presents an initial timeline of critical steps for the operation of the WGs that is further developed and enriched by the results of the Co-creation workshop in terms of performance monitoring and impact assessment. Each WG will meet on a semestrial basis, in terms of an online meeting with a duration of less than 2 hours. The facilitation of meetings will be undertaken by a selected Lighthouse Expert, who will set the goal of each meeting and propose the subject and agenda of each meeting’s discussion. Also, during the course of the project, two (2) Mobilization and Mutual Learning Workshops are foreseen - with an estimated duration of 2-3 hours, in which the WGs’ Members will be invited. The MMLs aim to collect suggestions, recommendations, and ideas for further improving the WGs outputs . The semestrial meetings (1st WGs’ Meeting in November 2023, 2nd WGs’ Meeting in May 2024, and 3rd WGs’ meeting in November 2024) of the WGs are going to feed the first MML(in December 2024), whose results will feed the plenary meeting (in May 2025). After all, the second MML (in June 2025) will be fed by the plenary meeting in order to improve the recommendations and outputs of the WGs. In M24 (August 2024) a report of the outputs and results along with their assessment with a specific indicator will be included in D2.3“Actionable results from WGs and MML workshop - Initial Version”. An update of the rest of the meetings as well as the outcomes of MML will be included in D2.3“Actionable Results from WGs and MML workshop – Final Version”.

Figure 5. Timeplan of 4WGs and MML Workshops

The provided table below offers a comprehensive outline of the agenda topics for discussion during the meetings of the four distinct WGs. Each WG convenes to address specific facets of each energy section which undertakes, ensuring a focused and systematic approach to collaboration. The table succinctly captures the essence of these discussions, providing with a clear roadmap of the subjects that will be deliberated upon within each meeting.

Table 10. WGs topics of discussion as per action list

1st Meeting M15 Nov 2023	Topic: Solutions for driving the development and adoption of renewable electricity & Skills Gap impacting its full deployment potential Expected Recommendations 1-2	Topic: Solutions for driving the development and adoption of sustainable mobility & Skills Gap impacting its full deployment potential Expected Recommendations 1-2	Topic: Solutions for driving the development and adoption of renewable heat & Skills Gap impacting its full deployment potential Expected Recommendations 1-2	Topic: Solutions for driving the development and adoption of renewable fuels and biofuels & Skills Gap impacting its full deployment potential Expected Recommendations 1-2
2nd Meeting M21 May 2024	Topic: Directions for regulatory shifts to shape favourable environment for sustainable renewable electricity & Skills Gap impacting its full deployment potential diffusion Expected Recommendations 1-2	Topic: Directions for regulatory shifts to shape favourable environment for sustainable mobility & Skills Gap impacting its full deployment potential diffusion Expected Recommendations 1-2	Topic: Directions for regulatory shifts to shape favourable environment for renewable heat & Skills Gap impacting its full deployment potential diffusion Expected Recommendations 1-2	Topic: Directions for regulatory shifts to shape favourable environment for renewable fuels and biofuels & Skills Gap impacting its full deployment potential diffusion Expected Recommendations 1-2
3rd Meeting M27 Nov 2024	Topic: Guidelines for educational /training programs to facilitate skilling reskilling upskilling	Topic: Guidelines for educational /training programs to facilitate skilling reskilling upskilling	Topic: Guidelines for educational /training programs to facilitate skilling reskilling upskilling	Topic: Guidelines for educational /training programs to facilitate skilling reskilling upskilling

	<p>in renewable Electricity & Skills Gap impacting its full deployment potential</p> <p>Expected Recommendations: 1-2</p>	<p>in sustainable mobility & Skills Gap impacting its full deployment potential</p> <p>Expected Recommendations: 1-2</p>	<p>in renewable heat & Skills Gap impacting its full deployment potential</p> <p>Expected Recommendations: 1-2</p>	<p>renewable fuels and biofuels & Skills Gap impacting its full deployment potential</p> <p>Expected Recommendations: 1-2</p>
<p>1st MML M28 Dec 2024</p>	<p>Topic: collect suggestions, recommendations, and ideas for further improving the WGs outputs. (Details about the topic will be defined, as soon as the respective task starts in M13 September 2023)</p> <p>As activities of MMLs are more open, WG members, Advisory Board Members and other stakeholders will be invited to exchange views and know-how. WGs members will be encouraged to participate based on their interests and availability.</p>			
<p>Plenary M33 May 2025</p>	<p>Topic: Identify new jobs and skills required in RES</p> <p>Translate technological advantages into educational/training needs in RES</p> <p>All members from the four WGs participate in the plenary meeting.</p>			
<p>2nd MML M34 June 2025</p>	<p>Topic: collect suggestions, recommendations, and ideas for further improving the WGs outputs (Details about the topic will be define, as soon as the respective task begins in M13 September 2023)</p>			

3.6 Main point of Reference

WG Manager – Administration

The WG Manager (Q-PLAN INTERNATIONAL), having an administrative role, will handle communications and interactions with WGs and their members and monitor their engagement to ensure smooth operation and meaningful results. For this purpose, a WG member Matrix (Annex X) has been developed to keep track of participation in activities and to ensure meaningful, results oriented interaction whilst a balanced engagement of all WG members is achieved. WG Manager will create a communication path (chat) for fast communication between the members and easy exchange of ideas.

The WG Member Matrix has been created as a dedicated tool to keep track and monitor the engagement of WG members in project activities. The Stakeholder Matrix will be updated by the WG

manager after every activity with a view to monitoring and documenting the results of the project in this respect and, if necessary, take action to ensure the effectiveness of the mechanism.

The WG Manager will be responsible for the organisation of the meeting, (agenda, invitations) and also will be the main contact point for any inquiry, complaint or concern about any aspect of the experience and a member of the WGs.

Lighthouse Experts

During the course of the project four (4) lighthouse experts (LHE) will coordinate and support the WGs. LHEs are persons with technical expertise in each WG thematic focus. The LHE, based on the topic of each meeting will prepare questions and main focus of discussion of each meeting, will chair and facilitate the discussion, will propose interaction solutions (slido, post-it, voting etc.) in order to keep the participation of members active and engaging. Moreover, the LHE will encourage fast communication between the members through a chosen tool. Last but not least, the LHE will be responsible for writing a brief report on the results of each meeting. The brief report will be delivered on a given template (Annex 8.3), that has been created by the WG Manager (Q-PLAN), also attaching the meeting agenda (Annex 8.2), participant list and basic outcomes. The most important task to derive from the WG meeting are **20 recommendations** collected at the end of all WG meetings. Indicatively, the recommendations may be policy recommendations, guidelines for local authorities, best practice recommendations, municipal directives, Improvement strategies, development blueprints, progress roadmap etc.

3.7 Remuneration

A remuneration is foreseen for the WG members in the maximum amount of 1000€ (for all 3 years of project duration). To receive the fee, the WG member has to participate in all WG meetings (4 meetings in total), and to issue an invoice. In case a company is represented by different WG members in different meetings, it has the right to issue an invoice as a company, if all the representatives are official WG members. The invoice is addressed to SKILLBILL Coordinator, including the elements stated below:

AzzeroCO2, Via Genova 23, 00184 Roma; Italy

VAT Number

Fiscal Authority

Justification: Participation in the [Name of the WG] WG Meetings under SKILLBILL Project (CON. NO. 101075587)/Horizon Europe

The contribution of WG members could also be on a **pro bono basis**. Moreover, participation in the WGs is **entirely voluntary**. There will be no adverse consequences if a WG member decides not to participate or to withdraw at any stage. In fact, WG members may withdraw their participation at any time by informing the WG Manager (Q-PLAN INTERNATIONAL). They may also request for their data to be withdrawn without giving any reason and without prejudice. Anonymous data already collected will be used because this information cannot be traced back to a specific person, but no further data or input will be collected, nor any other procedure will be carried out in relation to the specific member. In case of withdrawal from WG activities or non-show to a WG meeting, the member acknowledges the rule to receive no fee foreseen. In case of withdrawal, the Member is encouraged to offer a substitute person with relevant interest in the WG activities/discussions to assure the flow of WG work and success of results.

3.8 Term of Reference

The Terms of Reference (ToR) is a critical document that outlines the scope, objectives, and guidelines for WG members, addressed to WG members. It serves as a blueprint, defining the purpose, responsibilities, and expected outcomes of the WG. The ToR includes details about the project's timeline, remuneration, and key performance indicators. It also clarifies the roles and responsibilities of WG members, LHE and WG Manager. The document plays a pivotal role in providing a common understanding of the project's goals and parameters, ensuring that all participants are aligned and working towards a unified vision. Additionally, the ToR serves as a reference point for evaluating progress and outcomes, enabling effective project management and accountability throughout the initiative's lifecycle. (see Annex V for details).

Figure 6. Terms of Reference

3.9 Risks and Mitigation Measures

During the establishment of WGs, there are some critical risks that may occur and affect the expected structures and their operations. The following table summarizes the critical risks relative to the establishment of WGs, as provided in DoA Part A, “List of Critical Risks” table, along with others that may arise

Table 11. Risk and Mitigation Measures for the WGs Operation

Risk Number	Description	Proposed Mitigation Measure
1	Stakeholders not involved properly Low probability / Medium Impact	Potential stakeholders have been already identified, and the consortium network will guarantee that other stakeholders will be involved. A remuneration is foreseen for them also.
2	Low number of knowledge holders participating in WGs' meeting Low probability / High impact	WGs will facilitate stakeholder engagement and mobilization. In addition, SKILLBILL partners are linked with networks and communities in the energy sector, which can be leveraged to engage further stakeholders.

Risk Number	Description	Proposed Mitigation Measure
3	Risk of conflicts arising between WG members due to differing opinions or priorities Low probability / Low Impact	Foster a respectful and inclusive environment, appoint a skilled facilitator to manage discussions, and establish conflict resolution mechanisms to address disagreements constructively.
4	Risk of miscommunication or lack of clarity leading to misunderstandings and misaligned objectives Low probability / Low Impact	Ensure open and transparent communication channels, provide regular updates, and clarify roles and responsibilities to promote effective collaboration.
5	WG members losing interest or disengaging over time, lacking continuity and commitment.	Maintain regular communication, recognize and celebrate achievements, and foster a sense of ownership among members to sustain commitment.

By recognizing these risks and implementing appropriate mitigation measures, members can create a conducive and productive environment within the WG, maximizing the potential for successful outcomes in addressing the skills needed for the next generation of renewable energy technologies.

3.10 Working Groups Formation through a co-creation workshop

Co-creation workshops are an excellent way to form and structure common work in mutual contribution of all parties, following the methodology described in Section 2. WGs are considered an initiative that requires diverse expertise and collaboration from multiple stakeholders, so the CCW is acknowledged to be a fertile ground to set them up and co-decide on their operational model.

So a CCW was organized, where the WGs took center stage as catalysts for collaborative innovation. Facilitators provided a comprehensive explanation of the operational model for the WGs, detailing their roles, objectives, and expected outcomes. This clarity enabled participants to grasp the potential impact of their contributions and the value of their involvement. Engaged in a co-creative process, the attendees collectively shaped the topics of discussion for each WG. Through open dialogue and interactive sessions, they identified critical areas of interest within the energy sector and collaboratively defined the focus of each WG, ensuring alignment with the consortium's broader goals.

The WGs' operation model emphasized inclusivity and the quadruple helix approach, fostering a vibrant collaboration among academia, industry, government, and society. As participants shared their diverse perspectives and expertise, the atmosphere buzzed with creativity and enthusiasm. The co-creation workshop allowed for dynamic exchanges of ideas, paving the way for targeted and impactful discussions within the WGs. Co-creating the formation of the WGs through a workshop offered several advantages. Firstly, it ensured inclusivity, incorporating diverse perspectives and expertise, leading to comprehensive outcomes. Secondly, the workshop fostered ownership and engagement among participants, enhancing commitment to the initiative's success. Thirdly, the

process facilitated enhanced collaboration, knowledge sharing, and the building of professional relationships. Furthermore, it streamlined decision-making, focused discussions on relevant topics, and promoted transparency in communication. The co-creation approach also enabled flexibility and adaptability, ensuring the WGs remain relevant to addressing skills needs for upskilling and reskilling in the energy sector. With a skilled and committed workforce driving transformative advancements, the energy sector is poised for a sustainable and innovative future.

Within the context of the SKILLBILL Joint Stakeholder Initiative, a co-creation workshop (CCW) was held online on June 14th, 2023 by Q-PLAN International, engaging selected representatives from the project consortium, members of the SKILLBILL Advisory Board (AB) as well as external experts in renewable energy systems and sustainable biofuels, possible members of the WGs in European and international level. This activity was organised under the T2.2 “Co-design of Stakeholder Joint Initiative”.

A total 32 participants attended the CCWS of which 14 were external experts, 2 were members of the SKILLBILL AB, and 16 were members of the SKILLBILL consortium. Regarding the gender aspects ten (10) of them were women , and the rest twelve (22) were men.

The objective of the CCWS was to present the SKILLBILL project to participants, introduce the WGs to participants, meet each other and kick start the activities of the WGs. Specifically, during the CCWS codefined the specificities of the operational model

- (i) number of WGs,
- (ii) thematic focus of each WG,
- (iii) criteria for the selection of members,
- (iv) monitoring framework of the WG performance along with indicative KPIs,
- (v) meetings and estimated effort,
- (vi) rights and obligation of the membership,
- (vii) role of the lighthouse experts.
- (viii) co-design the topics that will be discussed during the WG meetings.

Ultimately, the main session of the workshop was designed to engage with key stakeholders in co-designing the topics that will be discussed during the WG meetings, in order to keep them active and get in touch with their interests.

Engagement of stakeholders

Q-PLAN prepared the communication pack (incl. invitation template e-mail, pdf with the main info of SKILLBILL and registration form, including an informed consent form for personal data, which are annexed in this deliverable) and shared it with the partners in order all of them to initiate their networks and engage possible members for the WGs, as described in details in Section 3.2

In total, 42 people expressed their interest in the workshop with their online registration.

Workshop preparation

The SKILLBILL co-creation workshop was planned to take place on the 14th of June 2023 in the form of a half-day. The SKILLBILL GA, stated that the CCW had to be planned and organized by virtual means, so it was organized in terms of an online event.

Q-PLAN, the task leader being responsible for the organisation of the co-creation workshop prepared an agenda of the event, the presentations, and the co-creation tools (see Annex XII, XIII). Apart from that, as a host, Q-PLAN sent official invitations to the registered people with links to connect.

The main parts of the workshop are presented in Agenda which was distributed two weeks prior to the event, to provide the context and the structure of the workshop. (see annex XI):

- Tour de la table and Ice Breaker
- SKILLBILL and objectives of the workshop
- Online tools explanation
- Session 1 of co-creation
- Session 2 of co-creation

The methodology followed for the delivering of the co-creation workshop and its co-creation session is concisely described in the following paragraphs.

Figure 7. SKILLBILL CCW Agenda

Software, Co-creation Tools, Breakout Rooms

To guarantee the participants could effectively interact and smoothly contribute to the discussion, three virtual platforms were selected for the workshop: Microsoft Teams, Mentimeter and Miro.

Software	Description	Advantages
<p>MS Teams</p>	MS Teams is a collaboration and real time communication platform, which is used for virtual meetings and webinars	The advantages are several, like the mobile accessibility, the security and the compliance, and the easy management of teams. Apart from that, allowed the participants to be divided in 4 parallel Breakout Rooms during the Co-Creation session
<p>Mentimeter</p>	Mentimeter is an interactive online tool, commonly used during co-creation activities with collaborative sessions where diverse stakeholders come together to jointly create and develop ideas and solutions.	As an online tool, it allows participants to engage in real-time activities and provide feedback during workshops. Some of its advantages could be the real-time engagement, the increased participation, the

Software	Description	Advantages
<p data-bbox="341 633 400 663">Miro</p>	<p data-bbox="608 333 1038 712">Miro is a collaborative online whiteboard platform that enables teams to work together simultaneously, in real-time, whether online or offline, regardless of their physical location. It provides a digital canvas for brainstorming, ideation, project planning, and visual collaboration.</p>	<p data-bbox="1066 226 1430 293">user-friendly application and the direct outcome.</p> <p data-bbox="1066 353 1430 696">With Miro users collaborate visually in real time and is ideal for remote teams. Miro provides a wide range of templates, it is versatile and flexible, facilitates brainstorming and ideation, with easy to share and save boards.</p>

Microsoft Teams’ breakout rooms is a feature that allows meeting organizers to divide participants into smaller groups during virtual meetings. Breakout rooms were found useful for facilitating focused discussions, brainstorming sessions, collaborative work, or team-building activities, and were used for Session II of the SKILLBILL co-creation workshop.

Promotion

Promoting a co-creation workshop effectively is essential to attract the right participants and ensure its success. As video content tend to be more engaging and shareable, Q-PLAN prepared 5 promotional videos (see Annex XIV) on the SKILLBILL co-creation workshop. The idea was to create catchy short promotional videos explaining the workshop’s value and what participants could expect, and some videos in the form of countdown a few days before the workshop. With the support of SKILLBILL Dissemination Manager, WHIRE Research SRL (WR), they were disseminated through the SKILLBILL official channels.

Apart from the videos, the most important step of promotion were the personal invitations to the key stakeholders, industry influencers and experts whose participation could significantly enhance the workshop’s impact, and consequently the WGs outcomes. Such invitation, often followed by phone calls as a direct means of communication, was sent by all partners through the engagement process described in details in previous sections, to their networks and taking into account the initial mapping under the T2.1 "Stakeholder community mapping and user research to better appreciate current training needs and skilling practices" if possible and the guidelines from the task leader following the communication pack methodology.

Delivering the co-creation workshop

The welcome session of the CCW set the tone for an exciting and collaborative journey. In this brief but impactful introduction, participants were warmly greeted, and the workshop's objectives and agenda were outlined. The facilitators emphasized the importance of each individual's contribution and encouraged an open and inclusive environment. This welcome session created a sense of belonging and enthusiasm, inspiring participants to actively engage in the co-creation process ahead.

The "Tour de la Table" and ice breaker session in the co-creation workshop set the stage for dynamic collaboration. During the "Tour de la Table," participants introduced themselves using online tools (Miro & Mentimeter), fostering a friendly and inclusive atmosphere. The ice breaker activities engaged attendees, encouraging them to interact and break down barriers. These sessions enhanced team bonding, stimulate creativity, and paved the way for constructive idea sharing throughout the workshop.

The Icebreaker – Online tools explanation session in the CCW introduced participants to the digital tools that will enhance their collaborative experience. In this concise session, facilitators demonstrated the functionality and features of the online tools, ensuring everyone felt comfortable using them. The interactive demonstration fostered a sense of confidence among participants, empowering them to actively contribute and collaborate effectively throughout the workshop, making the co-creation process seamless and engaging.

The co-creation session of the workshop was an engaging and collaborative experience. The organiser presented an operational model of WGs, outlining their roles and objectives. Seeking valuable insights, attendees were encouraged to provide feedback on their satisfaction level using Mentimeter polls. This real-time interaction allowed the organizer to gauge their responses instantly. Furthermore, by utilizing Miro, a digital whiteboard, to foster creativity, participants shared additional ideas, suggestions, and brainstormed together. The combination of Mentimeter and Miro facilitated an inclusive environment, enabling all participants to actively contribute with their thoughts, ensuring a dynamic and productive co-creation process that enriched the overall workshop outcomes.

During the second session, the attendees were divided into four breakout rooms to delve deeper into the topics of discussion for the WGs. Leveraging the collaborative features of Miro, each group was engaged with fruitful discussion, sharing ideas, and visualizing its thoughts on the digital canvas. Miro allowed the groups to co-create diagrams, mind maps, and other visual representations, fostering a dynamic and interactive environment. The breakout rooms facilitated focused and intimate discussions, enabling participants to explore different perspectives and work collectively towards innovative solutions. This utilization of Miro not only enhanced productivity but also ensured that the diverse expertise and insights of each group member were effectively harnessed for the success of the CCW.

Upon reconvening, all attendees shared the outcomes of their breakout sessions, through a breakout room rapporteur assigned by each group, presenting the results and feedback to assess the WGs' progress. Key indicators were discussed, evaluating the effectiveness and impact of the collaborative efforts. The comprehensive presentation enabled a holistic view of the workshop's achievements by all of the participants and identified areas for further improvement. This collective sharing of insights allowed participants to reflect on their contributions and fostered a sense of ownership in the co-creation process, fostering an environment of continuous learning and growth.

In the closing thank-you session, Q-PLAN extended heartfelt gratitude to all participants for their valuable contributions. Their active engagement and collaborative spirit have made this CCW a resounding success. Together, the participants have achieved meaningful outcomes, and shared the joy to continue this journey of innovation and teamwork in the future.

Participation

The participation of attendees in the CCW was notably positive and enthusiastic. Throughout the session, participants displayed genuine interest on the theme, actively engaging with discussions, and providing valuable insights. Their enthusiasm and commitment to the co-creation process created a dynamic and inclusive environment. The diverse perspectives that were shared by the

attendees enriched the discussions, leading to a comprehensive understanding of the challenges and opportunities at hand. Their valuable contributions played a pivotal role in shaping the outcomes of the workshop, reinforcing the significance of co-creation in driving successful and meaningful initiatives. The table below presents the participants that attended the CCW.

Table 12. List of participants

Name*	Organisation	Details
Andromachi Kalaouzi	Q-PLAN INTERNATIONAL	Partner
Dimitra Kyriakopoulou	Q-PLAN INTERNATIONAL	Partner
Ilaria Bientinesi	AzzeroCO2	Coordinator
External Expert 1	Eco Vibes	Possible Member of WGs
Tapani Kultaranta	Helsinki Vocational Institut	AB Member
Enrico Facci	AzzeroCO2	Partner
External Expert 2	Košice Self-governing region	Possible Member of WGs
Mona Roman	METROPOLIA	Partner
Anastasios Galatsopoulos	WHITE RESEARCH	Partner
Esa Toukoniitty	METROPOLIA	Partner
External Expert 3	Slovak Association of the Photovoltaic Industry and RES	Possible Member of WGs
Prodromos Gkalimanis	Q-PLAN INTERNATIONAL	Partner in relevant RES project, RES expert
Konstantinos Dasopoulos	Q-PLAN INTERNATIONAL	Partner in relevant RES project, RES expert
Eleonora Ivanova	Bulgarian-Romanian Chamber of Commerce and Industry	AB Member
External Expert 4	EDP NEW	Possible Member of WGs
Emanuele Bertolani	Sinergie	Partner
External Expert 5	Slovak Business Agency	
Stania Druskova	PEDAL	Partner
Alessandro Rosati	AzzeroCO2	Partner
External Expert 6	EDP NEW	Possible Member of WGs

Antti Tohka	METROPOLIA	Partner
External Expert 7	IHU	Possible member of WGs
Fouladvand, J. (Javanshir)	Uni Utrecht	Partner
External Expert 8	Friends of the Earth-CEPA	Possible member of WGs
External Expert 9	Slovak Business Agency	
External Expert 10	Technical University of Kosice & Kosice-Self Government Region & SBaA & Promatech Centre	Possible member of WGs
David Sanchez	Uni Sevilla	Partner
External Expert 11	NTUA	Possible Member of WGs
Rosales Carreon, J.	Uni Utrecht	Partner
Johannes Vollmer	EREF	Partner
External Expert 12	ANETH SA DEVELOPMENT AGENCY OF THESSALONIKI	Possible Member of WGs
Gabriele Loreti	Uni Tuscia	Partner

*The external experts in the table are kept in anonymity due to GDPR requirements.

After the co-creation workshop

The Task Leader and the host of the event, Q-PLAN, in order to express its gratitude to the attendees, and to show that their presence was valued and appreciated, sent an e-mail to share follow – up information including the useful links (Miro) and the presentation of the workshop. The most important idea behind that step was to build and strengthen relations with the attendees and future members of the WGs.

The organizer of the CCW took the initiative to gather participant feedback through a Google Form, aiming to gauge overall satisfaction with the event. The results were overwhelmingly positive, highlighting the success of the workshop across various dimensions. Participants expressed high satisfaction levels in terms of content, quality, timing, knowledge exchange, and the freedom to express themselves. Remarkably, 80% of respondents found the co-creation workshop to be "very much informative," while the remaining 20% found it "very informative." Moreover, a significant 80% of participants deemed the information provided about membership in the WGs and the associated efforts to be "helpful," with 20% rating it as "very much helpful." In open comments, attendees suggested a slight reduction in the icebreaker session and a desire for more time allocated to the co-creation activities, though acknowledging the challenge of balancing time constraints. Additionally, a few participants mentioned encountering internet connectivity issues during the workshop. This feedback serves as valuable insights for fine-tuning future events and optimizing the participant experience.

3.11 Sustain the Working Groups

WGs will settle cooperation initiatives that may sustain their discussions beyond the project duration. Being four already formulated networks, the WGs may voluntarily be expanded also involving other members on a pro bono basis if the members wish to expand the WG lifespan. The 4 WGs may work in parallel with SKILLBILL Master to feed academia with important information deriving directly from the market/ stakeholders, keeping up with tech progress, and future skills required. If members decide to go forward with the WGs, they should announce it and disseminate it widely and continue communicating with the dedicated communication tool (chat) to make sure that all impacted teams are informed and brought into the initiative, and to ask for frequent input. Sustaining WGs beyond the end of the project requires careful planning and strategic measures to ensure longevity and continued impact. Such strategies are presented in the table below:

Table 13. Indicative strategies to sustain the Working Groups

Strategy	Brief Description
Engage Stakeholders	Involve key stakeholders from the energy sector, including industry leaders, government representatives, academia, and training institutions, to ensure a diverse and collaborative perspective in identifying skills needs.
Long-Term Vision	Develop a clear and long-term vision for the WGs, outlining their objectives, scope, and expected outcomes. This will provide a sense of purpose and direction, motivating members to stay engaged.
Data-Driven Approach	Utilize data and research to identify current and future skill needs in the energy sector. Conduct surveys, interviews, and research to understand the demands of new energy technologies and the associated skill gaps.
Industry Collaboration	Foster strong collaborations with energy companies, research institutions, and professional associations. These partnerships can provide valuable insights into industry trends and skill requirements.
Continuous Evaluation	Regularly assess the effectiveness and impact of the WGs' efforts. Adjust strategies as needed to address emerging skills demands and changing industry landscapes
Public-Private Partnerships	Seek support from both public and private sectors to ensure sustainable funding and resource availability for the WGs' initiatives.

Strategy	Brief Description
Training and Capacity Building:	Organize training programs and workshops to upskill and reskill the existing workforce in the energy sector. Encourage continuous professional development to stay abreast of new technologies and industry advancements.
Promote Awareness:	Raise awareness about the importance of skilling upskilling and reskilling within the energy sector. Highlight the benefits of these initiatives in meeting future energy demands and enhancing career opportunities.
Youth Engagement	Involve young professionals and students in the WGs to bridge the skills gap and foster a new generation of skilled workers in the energy sector.
Participatory Approach	Encourage active participation and ownership among WG members. Empower them to take the lead in driving initiatives and collaborating with other stakeholders.
Gender Equality Mainstreaming	Involve systematically integrating gender perspectives into all aspects of the group's functioning. This ensures that gender considerations are central to the group's goals, processes, and outcomes, fostering an inclusive and equitable environment.

By implementing these indicative strategies, the WGs can play a crucial role in addressing the skills needs of the energy sector, ensuring a skilled and competent workforce that can effectively translate the requirements of new energy technologies into practice, even beyond the course of the project if that falls under their interests.

4. Results

The results section of the co-creation workshop encapsulated the fruitful outcomes of a collective journey towards innovation and collaboration. This section highlights the key findings, transformative ideas, and tangible solutions that emerged from the workshop's dynamic interaction. Through extensive discussions and active engagement, participants contributed with their diverse expertise, fostering a wealth of fresh insights and perspectives. The results section presents a comprehensive overview of the identified challenges, the innovative strategies devised, and the actionable steps to follow. It served as a testament to the power of collaborative efforts and the significant impact of co-creation in driving positive change within the domain of focus.

4.1 Ice breaker

In the spirit of fostering an engaging and interactive co-creation workshop, this session initiated with a dynamic icebreaker, utilizing Mentimeter and Miro. Through Mentimeter, participants were asked to share their first destination after the COVID pandemic on a digital map, creating a vibrant tapestry of dream getaways. This light-hearted and enjoyable activity served as an excellent icebreaker, setting the stage for open communication and active involvement. Additionally, leveraging Miro, participants introduced themselves, providing key information about their names, organizations, and expertise in the renewable energy field. This interactive exercise not only cultivated a sense of camaraderie but also unveiled the diverse wealth of knowledge within the team and also let the participants get familiar with the tools that were about to be used throughout the CCW. Progressing in this report, the results of the icebreaker are presented, showcasing the positive impact of these interactive tools in fostering meaningful engagement and collaboration among the passionate participants.

Figure 8. Mentimeter results of ice breaker, regarding the destination the participants travelled after covid -19

The consensus among many attendees was that solar energy would take center stage, followed closely by bioenergy, as key pillars of the sustainable energy landscape. However, a diverse array of perspectives emerged, with others passionately advocating for the potential of hydrogen, wind power, and heat pumps as equally essential components of the RES mix. The CCW fostered an atmosphere of open-mindedness and collaboration, with participants recognizing the importance of striking a harmonious balance among various renewable sources. This vibrant exchange of ideas laid the groundwork for further exploration, guiding the WGs’ efforts to harness the full potential of diverse RES technologies and create a future of cleaner, greener, and more resilient energy systems.

4.3 Session I of co-creation: Operational Model

During the first session of the CCW, the facilitators introduced the operational model of the WGs to the participants. To gauge the attendees' satisfaction with the presented model, a dynamic voting process was conducted using Mentimeter. Participants were asked to rate their satisfaction on a scale from 1 to 5, by 1 indicating low satisfaction and 5 reflecting high satisfaction. This real-time polling approach allowed for quick and anonymous feedback, providing valuable insights into the participants' level of contentment with the operational model. The interactive nature of Mentimeter enabled a comprehensive assessment of the participants' sentiments, ensuring that their voices were heard, and their input factored into the workshop's progression. Additionally, to promote open dialogue and detailed feedback, the workshop integrated Miro, where participants further shared their thoughts and suggestions, fostering a collaborative environment that empowered the attendees to actively contribute to shaping the WGs’ initiatives.

Figure 11. Satisfaction on operational model

The results of the voting using Mentimeter during the first session of the co-creation workshop were overwhelmingly positive. Participants expressed high levels of satisfaction with the presented operational model of the WGs. The majority of attendees rated their satisfaction with the model at a 4 or 5 on the scale, indicating strong approval and enthusiasm for the proposed approach. This positive feedback provided a strong validation of the facilitators' efforts in designing a model that resonated well with the participants' expectations and objectives. The encouraging response from the attendees fuelled a sense of excitement and motivation to move forward with the CCW, ensuring

a collective commitment to the success of the WGs and the pursuit of transformative advancements in the renewable energy sector.

In a concerted effort to ensure inclusivity and gather diverse perspectives, the co-creation workshop utilized Miro as a collaborative digital platform. Participants actively engaged in discussions, sharing their valuable insights, and contributing to the co-creation process through this interactive tool. The culmination of their collective efforts is vividly depicted in a comprehensive figure, showcasing the results and outcomes of the workshop. This visually appealing representation captures the essence of the participants' ideas, opinions, and suggestions, offering a clear overview of the diverse perspectives and innovative solutions generated during the workshop. The figure serves as a powerful testament to the efficacy of the co-creation approach and the commitment to hearing and incorporating all voices in refining and optimizing the operational model of the WGs. Leveraging Miro as a collaborative space allowed for enhanced communication and collective problem-solving, ensuring that the WGs are equipped to drive transformative advancements in the renewable energy sector effectively.

Figure 12. Suggestion and improvements on Working Groups Operation

4.4 Session II of co-creation: Topics of discussion for the upcoming WG meetings

During a dynamic co-creation session, participants were eagerly invited to shape the upcoming meetings of the WGs based on their unique interests and expertise. Engaging in an open and inclusive dialogue, attendees enthusiastically contributed diverse topics for discussion, aligning with the WGs' objectives and expected outcomes. This interactive session empowered the participants to actively influence the future direction of the WGs, ensuring that the upcoming meetings would be both relevant and impactful. The exchange of ideas showcased the collective commitment of the participants to driving transformative advancements in the specific focus areas, setting the stage for meaningful collaborations and comprehensive outcomes in the renewable energy sector.

During the co-creation session, participants were actively engaged in proposing topics for discussion relevant to their interests and the expected outcomes of the upcoming meetings of the WGs.

Participants were divided into breakout rooms as described in the previous section, where they presented and elaborated on their proposals to their smaller groups. These breakout sessions allowed for in-depth discussions and feedback, empowering participants to refine and shape their ideas collectively. The co-creation session served as a powerful platform for diverse voices to contribute meaningfully, laying the groundwork for the WGs future meetings to be guided by the shared vision and expertise of the participants.

Following the breakout sessions, where participants presented and discussed their proposals, the CCW utilized the Miro voting tool to determine the most prominent topics for discussion. Each proposal was displayed on a digital canvas within Miro, and participants were given the opportunity to cast their votes for the topics they found most compelling and relevant to the WGs’ objectives. As the votes were tallied, the most prominent topics emerged, as presented in the following table, guiding the WGs in setting their agendas for the upcoming meetings. The democratic nature of the voting process ensured that the final selection of topics truly represented the interests and aspirations of the participants, fostering a sense of ownership.

Figure 13. Miro Board used during the second session of the co-creation workshop

Below are the results of the co-creation session, (in order to be visible, the notes inserted by the participants in post-it stickers during the online CCW, are copied in the cells of the following tables in random order), showcasing the most prominent topics for discussion as being voted by the participants:

Table 14. Indicative (and not restrictive) topics of discussion for the solutions for driving the development and adoption of sustainable renewable energy and fuels techs

Solutions for driving the development and adoption of sustainable renewable energy and fuels techs				
support projects	community	Politics / political decisions / steering	targeting young citizens / students in schools	Awareness raising actions
increase skills		self-sufficient community energy grid	Life-cycle cost analysis (to overcome e.g. Financial risks)	(New) financial instruments that would help develop RES processes *
Just transition Fund for reskilling workers from the carbon-		Targeted programmes for marginalised (i.e. Roma, migrant) communities	Sector integration	Transposition of relevant EU legislation

Solutions for driving the development and adoption of sustainable renewable energy and fuels techs			
intensive industries/regions *			
instructions/steps for better home energy usage	Future oriented energy plans (to overcome inappropriate regulations) *	support project community	Setting up financial tools for citizens/companies to cover some of the costs
Enabling the set-up of energy communities	Lack of tools to bridge the gap from technology level to reach the market - Awareness level activities		

*In green, the most important topics are highlighted

Table 15. Indicative (and not restrictive) topics of discussion for the directions for regulatory shifts that help share a favourable environment for sustainable renewable energy and fuels tech diffusion

Directions for regulatory shifts that help share a favourable environment for sustainable renewable energy and fuels tech diffusion			
Political & regulatory barriers*	societal barriers (lack of know-how, NIMBYism, information issues, reluctance to change)*	bureaucracy	Ineffective & unstable policies
Excessive & complex procedures	Technical (ineffective grid development, insufficient infrastructure)	Inappropriate regulations => measure to overcome this: future-oriented energy plans	Economic and market barriers (such as lack of financing options, high initial costs, long payback time, investment risk, market uncertainty) => measures: live cycle analysis; external funding options*

*In green, the most important topics are highlighted

Table 16. Indicative (and not restrictive) topics of discussion for the guidelines for education / training programs to facilitate skilling, reskilling and upskilling

Guidelines for education / training programs to facilitate skilling, reskilling and upskilling			
Make sure that the programs stay modernized and actualized so that students can learn new technologies*	Establish common frameworks in Europe	Integrated internships between universities and companies working in the field	Important to train the ability to learn/teach new skills rather than a specific skill
transferability of skills	synergy between companies and Universities	qualification standards required	Innovation centres to increase the skills and increase communication between education centres and companies
support of policy makers	practical skills are required more than just theoretical	prepare an action plan/strategy for the RES for the development of skills and define the transition at national level*	clear definition of green jobs
Fuse regulatory and policy aspects in education/training procedure - raise up the trust and awareness on new technologies and investment potential*	online gamification tools	energy sector is evolving, so new skills are always required	synergy between companies and Universities*

*In green, the most important topics are highlighted

Table 17. Indicative (and not restrictive) topics of discussion for the identification of new jobs and skills required for the shaping of the next generation of sustainable renewable energy and fuels technologies

Identification of new jobs and skills required for the shaping of the next generation of sustainable renewable energy and fuels technologies			
Communication	knowledge on the RES local markets	knowledge on speculation of solar energy	project management skills

<p style="text-align: center;">Identification of new jobs and skills required for the shaping of the next generation of sustainable renewable energy and fuels technologies</p>				
Media Literacy	System Skills*	Thinking	digital computerised systems, programming skills	skills- financial analysis
Creativity	Collaboration		Sharing knowledge, educational environments and materials. Systematic co-operation together with educational institutes and industry.	digitalisation is crucial for the development of the digital skills.
information handling	Social and governance skills		Critical Thinking Skills	have understanding on the environment
technology specific skills -enter new fields of RES*	create boards that meet periodically-discussion on curricula development		lack of communication between Unis/ VET and Industry	communication skills
deeper understanding of maintenance and use of instruments	skill in designing systems		Learn how to lead and manage expertise	environmental considerations within the life cycle of the RES projects*
business associations like chambers of commerce can mediate communication b/n industry and educational sector	Learn how to lead and manage expertise			

*In green, the most important topics are highlighted

4.5 Indicative Key Performance Indicators

To enhance the monitoring framework and ensure its effectiveness, the co-creation workshop solicited valuable contributions from the participants regarding indicators. Recognizing the expertise and insights of the diverse group, participants were encouraged to provide input on relevant key performance indicators for the WGs that could accurately measure and assess the progress and impact of the initiatives undertaken by the WGs. Through interactive discussions and collaborative brainstorming, participants actively shared their ideas and suggestions, shaping a comprehensive set of indicators aligned with the objectives and expected outcomes of the renewable energy projects. By involving the participants in this crucial aspect of the monitoring framework, the workshop fostered a sense of ownership and commitment, ensuring that the chosen indicators truly reflect the shared vision and aspirations of the stakeholders. These participant-driven indicators will play a pivotal role in evaluating the success and effectiveness of the renewable energy initiatives, empowering the WGs to make informed decisions and drive positive change in the energy sector.

Figure 14. KPIs in Miro Board

The table below presents the results.

Table 18. Indicative KPIs for the assessment of the outcomes of the WGs

Category	Indicative KPIs				
Impact	people trained in each area	trained	Number of projects planned	raised sustainable behaviours	# of barriers overcome
Effectiveness	how effective do you feel the LHE communicate the goals of each meeting?	level of continuous learning and growth of all members	frequency of internal communication by the LHE		feedback taking into consideration after each session of WG

Category	Indicative KPIs				
Efficiency	number of Policy Recommendations in each meeting	number of decisions made in each meeting	Attendance & Punctuality	number of ideas generated	
Sustainability	number of training activated that can last long	amount of initiatives that can be easily replicated	cleaner cities - less emissions and waste	number of people trained/ CV upskilled/reskilled	number of synergies established (between educational centers and industries) (or between other entities)
Team Working	active participation of everyone	fair treatment of members	number of interactions between groups	Collaboration outside of the project	
Stakeholder Engagement	number of involved members in decisions	stakeholders satisfaction with meetings	Attendance & Punctuality	public - private subsidies	synergies with local authorities

5. Conclusions

Overall positive successful / interactions

In culmination, the journey of the SKILLBILL project has been marked by a series of deliberate and strategic steps, each contributing to the establishment of a collaborative platform dedicated to advancing sustainable renewable energy and fuel technologies. The project embarked on a comprehensive design phase, orchestrating the blueprint for the Joint Stakeholder Initiative. This involved meticulous deliberation to determine the thematic focuses, assemble the monitoring framework, design the selection criteria, and formulate an operational model that would set the course for subsequent actions.

As the project unfolded, its emphasis transitioned towards fostering active engagement with stakeholders, an essential cornerstone for a successful collaborative endeavor. In May 2023, the careful preparation of official membership documents was developed, including the composition of the Terms of Reference (ToRs) and the formulation of acceptance declarations. The subsequent months bore witness to active stakeholder engagement, creating the fertile ground for fruitful cooperation.

June 2023 marked a significant milestone with the execution of a dynamic co-creation workshop. The workshop brought together the minds of WG members, SKILLBILL Advisory Board participants, and project partners to collaboratively shape a detailed operational model. This model laid down the guiding principles for the Working Groups, elucidating their goals, responsibilities, and timelines.

In August 2023, the project is positioned at the brink of delivering its anticipated outcomes. However, this juncture also serves as a precursor to more extensive and dynamic phases lying ahead. In September and October 2023, the formalization of official memberships for stakeholders who have already demonstrated their interest will take precedence. This phase embodies the commitment and sets the stage for the WG activities.

The impending months usher in a new era as the spotlight shifts to the Working Groups (WGs). These specialized collaborative structures, each with a thematic focus encompassing sustainable and renewable electricity, mobility, heat, and fuels, symbolize the heart of SKILLBILL's pursuit. Comprising 6-8 members, these WGs are primed to be powerhouses of idea exchange, innovation, and education. Their convergence, marked by diversity and expertise, will navigate the development of the next generation of renewable energy systems, illuminating skill gaps and educational needs within the energy sector.

The culmination of meticulous planning, robust stakeholder engagement, and an illuminating co-creation workshop paves the way for renewable energy advancement. The collaborative spirit of SKILLBILL sets the tone for a future characterized by sustainable growth, where each stakeholder's expertise and passion contribute to realizing a net-zero energy landscape. The project's journey has been marked by participative and synergy efforts, and as the pages of SKILLBILL achievements evolve, the Working Groups will continue to contribute to progress and innovation, propelling society closer to a greener and more sustainable future.

6. ANNEX: Attachments

Annex I: Intro Pack SKILLBILL

SKILLBILL INFO PACK

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1. SKILLBILL Overview

SKILLBILL in a nutshell

The transition to a low-carbon energy system is a societal challenge not just a technical problem. The complexity of energy policy and the issues that policymakers deal with are not necessarily those that energy consumers face. The basic idea underlying the project is that the knowledge should be diffused at different levels, qualitatively appropriate both to train adequate number of workers and to increase awareness in renewable energy, reaching a more social and inclusive Europe. With that in mind, **SKILLBILL aims to pave the way to different forms of training and education in order to meet new skills requirements in RES field as well as induce citizens and stakeholders to get interested or involved in renewables** regardless the initial level of education, their working position and their gender. The technological renewable energy potential can be reached by increasing hard and soft skills of potential users and stakeholders, developing interest in the topic and having clear and appropriate approaches, such as tools and learning modules using suitable language. SKILLBILL recognizes the need for lifelong learning opportunities on RES (Renewable Energy Systems), in order to fight functional illiteracy and to maintain and update skills of workers, technicians and designers, on the field, to promote renewable energy systems. Moreover, SKILLBILL acknowledges the importance of raising awareness of the general public, so to achieve wider RES (Renewable Energy Systems) deployment.

Goal and Scope of SKILLBILL

The **ultimate goal** of SKILLBILL is to contribute to the implementation of the European Green Deal priorities, Circular Economy Action Plan and the Action Plan on Critical Raw Materials and the achievement of a climate-neutral Europe by 2050.

SKILLBILL's **overall objective** is to develop a large and strong foundation for the growth and acceleration of renewable energy's deployment, thanks to engaging with stakeholders of the whole chain, diffusing scientific culture and skilling multi-level workers.

Thus, SKILLBILL's **main objectives** are:

- Steer the development of a greener, more effective and pervasive next generation of sustainable technology
- Launch the point of reference for qualitative information on RES and promote and accelerate the development of sustainable solutions (Green Portal)
- Develop an advanced permanent education program on RES (Renewable Energy Systems) at European level
- Develop a technical practical permanent Vocational Education Training program on RES (Renewable Energy Systems)
- Reduce gender gap in STEM (Science, Technology, Engineering, Mathematics)
- Increase awareness, fighting against lack of information, bad quality of educational material and the phenomenon of functional illiteracy, therefore improving inclusiveness on RES (Renewable Energy Systems)

SKILLBILL INFO PACK

2. Purpose and role of Stakeholder Joint Initiative

Overview

SKILLBILL foresees the creation of a Stakeholder Joint Initiative, engaging stakeholders of all seven involved consortium countries and even beyond, in pan-European level. Experts derive from the whole value chain of Renewable Energy Systems (independent experts with wide recognition and proven expertise in the fields of renewable energy, sustainable economy, Vocational Educational Training, and academic education). The mission of the Stakeholder Joint Initiative is to develop a large and strong foundation for the growth and acceleration of renewable energy development, with a view to a greener, more effective, and pervasive next generation of sustainable technology.

The Stakeholder Joint Initiative will be formed via a **co-creation workshop**, which take place on the 14th of June 2023 at 11.00 CET. Stakeholders will be involved to offer their transdisciplinary knowledge for the benefit of the project, sharing their views, past experiences and perceptions.

3. Working Groups within the context of the Stakeholder Joint Initiative

Overview

Four interdisciplinary Working Groups to discuss the technological and non-technological barriers for RES penetration will be created under the tasks of the Stakeholder Joint initiative. Stakeholders of the whole Quadruple Helix (academia, industries, public authorities, and citizens) will be invited to be actively involved in the Working Groups with the aim to push the development of the next generation techs towards the sustainability and circularity; as well as to align priorities and needs of the whole RES¹ value chain (from designers, tech providers, to end-users).

Each Working Group will focus on a targeted thematic. The thematic focus will be as follows:

1. Sustainable and Renewable Electricity	Power to grid and market of electricity: characteristics of power grid, variability of energy mix, operation of electricity market, incentive to promote the installation of renewable energy technologies for power generation.
---	--

¹ RES: Renewable Energy Systems

SKILLBILL INFO PACK

	<p>VRE² technologies: PV³ systems (small and large scale), wind turbines, interaction with the grid</p> <p>Dispatchable Renewable Energy Technologies: Hydroelectric, CSP⁴, linear collectors, geothermal and WHR⁶, Organic Rankine Cycle</p>
<p>2. Sustainable Mobility</p>	<p>Road Transport: Fuels and emissions of road vehicles (light and heavy), electric vehicles, hydrogen cars, biofuels (generation and distribution and storage), fast chargers for electric vehicles</p> <p>Air transport: Sustainable Aviation fuels, Hydrogen aircraft, Electric Air craft</p> <p>Maritime transport: carbon footprint of maritime transportation, sustainable marine fuels</p>
<p>3. Sustainable and Renewable Heat</p>	<p>Renewable heat technologies: geothermal, bioenergy (incl. CHP⁵), WHR⁶, electrical heating and district heating</p> <p>Sustainable heat in built environment: Insulation, heat pumps, solar energy, wood pellet, distinct heating and heat storage</p> <p>Industrial renewable heat</p>
<p>4. Sustainable and Renewable Fuels</p>	<p>Biofuels processes (gasification, syngas⁷, biooils / upgrading, biomass production and pre-treatment)</p> <p>Waste to Fuels, waste oils, HVO⁸, pyrolysis of biomass / gasification, biowaste to biogas</p> <p>Renewable energy to chemicals and fuels (power to hydrogen, methane, ammonia, syngas process)</p>

² VRE: Variable Renewable Energy

³ PV: Photovoltaic

⁴ CSP: Concentrated Solar Power

⁵ CHP: Combined Heat and Power

⁶ WHR: Waste Heat Recovery

⁷ Syngas: Synthesis gas, is a mixture of hydrogen and carbon monoxide

⁸ HVO: Hydrotreated Vegetable Oil

SKILLBILL INFO PACK

The Working Groups will incentivize and expedite the adoption of sustainable renewable energy and fuel technologies, encompassing “circularity by design” principles, and give meaningful directions for regulatory shifts. They will also address the identification of new jobs for the next generation of sustainable renewable energy and the skills required, with the aim to be included in an International Master and Vocational Training schemes, both created under SKILLBILL, translating technological advantages into education / training needs.

Membership and Benefits

Being part of the Working Group means to participate directly in the project and support the project work, as well as its outcomes. Working Group members will be asked to sign a Declaration of Acceptance of their membership, taking into consideration the Terms of Reference and the Informed Consent Form, respecting the GDPR rules. They are going to meet via electronic means (online, cca 2 hour-meetings) **every six months** (November 2023, May 2024, November 2024, May 2025), discuss on the provided topics aiming to come into concrete solutions.

WG Members will be **benefited** by:

- getting early information about preliminary results, work progress and planned activities,
- being the main actors for raising the acceptance of results.
- shaping the environment and future of RES
- expanding their network of interest and networking opportunities

Members are welcome to raise questions and objections. Their additional input and comments will significantly contribute to maximizing the usability and acceptance of project results.

More specifically, the Working Group members are invited to:

- a) Co-create and give feedback on Working Groups operation via an on-line workshop along with other Joint Initiative stakeholders.
- b) Participate in Working Groups meetings (on semestrial basis)
- c) Participate in Mobilization and Mutual Learning Workshops, if interested
- d) Inform SKILLBILL Consortium about new and emerging issues on their sector of interest
- e) Offer their perspectives to dissemination activities, communicating SKILLBILL’s work to their internal and external networks

Each working group will be chaired by a Lighthouse Expert, who is going to coordinate the meeting and facilitate the discussion on each topic. The Lighthouse Experts will be assigned by the technical partners of the consortium, which are [EREF](#) and [AzzeroCO2](#). Having a technical background, the Lighthouse Expert will be responsible for setting the technical issues and the agenda for the discussion, animating the communication, facilitating the meetings and assuring that the meeting come up with the valuable knowledge and recommendations for the project.

The administrative support and the organisation of meetings will be undertaken by Q-PLAN to support the technical work of the Lighthouse Experts.

Planned Effort for Working Groups Members

SKILLBILL foresees one online meeting every six months for Working Groups members, which means 3 meetings within the thematic of each Working Group and one plenary at the project's end

SKILLBILL INFO PACK

involving all four WG members, in order to cross-fertilize ideas and improve the final outputs. The average duration of each WG meeting is going to be less than 2hours. Also, during the course of the project, two (2) Mobilizations and Mutual Learning Workshops are foreseen, while their duration is estimated about 2-3 hours, to which the Working Groups' Member will be invited to participate.

The invitation for the Working Groups semestrial meetings will be sent by the SKILLBILL responsible partner, Q-PLAN INTERNATIONAL, nominated as the Working Group Manager, at least 30 days prior the meeting. The invitation will include a draft agenda and a storyboard along with the expected output of each meeting. The Working Groups will meet online and may interact via electronic means.

Remuneration

A remuneration is foreseen for all Working Group members in the maximum amount of 1000€ (for all 3 years of project duration). To receive the fee, the WG member has to (i) be official members of the Working Groups (signing the Declaration of Acceptance taking into consideration the Terms of Reference and the Informed Consent Form, respecting the GDPR Rules), (ii) participate in all working group meetings (4 meetings in total), and (iii) to issue an invoice addressed to SKILLBILL Coordinator (AzzeroCO2, Italy). The participation and contribution of WG members could also be on a pro bono basis. There will be no adverse consequences if a WG member decides not to participate or to withdraw at any stage. In fact, WG members may withdraw their participation at any time by informing the WG Manager (Q-PLAN INTERNATIONAL). They may also request for their data to be withdrawn without giving a specific reason and without prejudice. Anonymous data collected will be used as this information cannot be traced back to a specific person. No additional data or input will be requested/collected, nor any other procedure will be carried out in relation to the specific member.

4. The Contact Person

The stakeholders of the Joint Initiative and the Working Groups members may contact:

- for any general issue, clarification or further details needed the Working Group Manager (Q-PLAN INTERNATIONAL)
- the technical issues, ideas and questions - can be either address directly to Lighthouse Expert directly or to Working Group Manager, who will get in contact with the Lighthouse Expert indirectly.

The contact persons in Q-PLAN INTERNATIONAL are Andromachi Kalaouzi (Project Consultant) and Dimitra Kyriakopoulou (Project Manager). For any question, feel free to contact them [here](#).

The project

SKILLBILL's overall objective is to develop a large and strong foundation for the growth and acceleration of renewable energy's deployment, thanks to engaging with stakeholders of the whole chain, diffusing scientific culture and skilling multi-level workers. The basic idea underling the project is that the knowledge should be diffused at several different levels and qualitatively appropriate both to train the adequate number of workers and to increase RES awareness and to reach a more social and inclusive Europe. The project aims at creating several pathways to induce target groups to get interested or involved in RES besides their initial level of education and their working position. It's important, beside the creation of instruments for the upskilling and reskilling of workers, technician and designers, to have awareness modules for unspecific public in order to fight against lack of information, bad quality material, gender gap and the phenomenon of functional illiteracy: it is widely documented that lifelong suitable learning process is the fundamental driver to support the development, maintenance and update of skills. Thus, SKILLBILL proposes concrete actions to accelerate the deployment of renewable energy at different levels to analyse and involve all the interested parts in open discussion using adequate language; create several different pathways to increase skills after having mapped knowledge gap and without gender prejudice; develop and implement innovative learning method; and evaluate the work performed.

Coordinator: **AZZERO CO2 SRL (AzzeroCO2)**

PARTNER		SHORT NAME
	AZZERO CO2 SRL	AzzeroCO2
	Q-PLAN INTERNATIONAL ADVISORS PC	Q-PLAN
	WHITE RESEARCH SPRL	WR
	UNIVERSITA DEGLI STUDI DELLA TUSCIA	UNITUS
	UNIVERSIDAD DE SEVILLA	USE
	METROPOLIA AMMATTIKORKEAKOULU OY	METROPOLIA
	UNIVERSITEIT UTRECHT	UU
	EUROPEAN RENEWABLE ENERGIES FEDERATION	EREF
	SINERGIE SOC CONS ARL	SINERGIE
	PEDAL CONSULTING SRO	PC

CONTACT US info@skillbill-project.eu **VISIT** www.skillbill-project.eu

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 @ SKILLBILL Project

Annex II: Registration and informed Consent Form

8/1/23, 4:17 PM

Co-creation Workshop

Co-creation Workshop

Within the context of [SKILLBILL](#) project, we are organising a dedicated online co-creation workshop with project partners, experts from the SKILLBILL Advisory Board, as well as key players in RES sector. Based on our planning, the workshop will be organised on 14th of June, 2023 at 11.00 CET. It will be held online, via Microsoft Teams platform, and its duration will be approximately 3 hours. After your registration, the workshop organisers will share with you the agenda, a calendar invitation and a link to join.

For any questions, please contact Andromachi Kalaouzi via [email](#)

* Indicates required question

1. Email *

2. Name *

3. Phone *

4. Field of Expertise

Mark only one oval.

Fuels

Heat

Electricity

Mobility

Other: _____

8/1/23, 4:17 PM

Co-creation Workshop

5. Organisation *

6. Position of the Organisation

7. Gender *

Mark only one oval.

- Female
- Male
- Non - Binary
- Prefer not to say

8. If you wish to already express your interest for **joining** one of the **4 Working Groups to be created in the context of SKILLBILL**, please tick the Working Group of your interest:

Check all that apply.

- Sustainable and Renewable Fuels
- Sustainable and Renewable Heat
- Sustainable and Renewable Electricity
- Sustainable Mobility

Informed Consent Form

Who we are:

We are [Q-PLAN](#)

[INTERNATIONAL](#) and we are contacting you in the context of SKILLBILL project funded by the European Union (Horizon Europe Framework Programme for Research and Innovation). A detailed description on how SKILLBILL handles personal data is presented in the project's [Privacy Policy](#) available through the project's [web page](#).

Project:

SKILLBILL- Skill to Boost Innovation and professional fulfilment in a sustainable economy (GA Number 101075587).

Partner:

Organisation Name: Q-PLAN INTERNATIONAL

Address: 11, El. Venizelou st., PC 551 33, Kalamaria, Thessaloniki, Greece

Phone: +30 2310 257277 | +30 2310 411 191

E-mail: info@qplan-intl.gr

Responsible Persons:

SKILLBILL Project Manager Dimitra Kyriakopoulou kyriakopoulou@qplan-intl.gr

Working Group Manager Andromachi Kalaouzi kalaouzi@qplan-intl.gr

Data Protection Officer Petros Papadionisiou papadionisiou@qplan-intl.gr

What we need from you?

We invite you to participate in the SKILLBILL Co–Creation Workshop to be held on 14th Jun, 2023. During the Workshop, participants will be introduced to the objectives and latest developments of the project. Via an open discussion, we would like to invite you to SKILLBILL Working Groups and gather your valuable feedback on the Working Groups operational plan.

To effectively carry out the activities of the Working Groups, we will need to process some of your personal data:

- Your contact details (full name, email);
- Some basic demographics (gender);
- Your professional info (organization, job position, field of expertise);

8/1/23, 4:17 PM

Co-creation Workshop

- Videos and photos, captured during your participation in the workshop

Why we need your data & what will we do with them?

We need your data to contact you in order to plan and carry out the aforementioned workshop and to resolve any ambiguities, questions and other issues that may arise after and as a result of the workshop. We also need to record your data to keep track of the workshop process, so as to be reported to the European Commission. The project's deliverables that will be derived by these activities will not include your personal data or any other information that could identify you. Your personal data will remain on our written notes (workshop's transcript).

We may share your data with a few other SKILLBILL project partners that are also involved in this task, named Lighthouse Experts, and will participate in the drafting of the relevant deliverables. We are also obliged to grant access to your data to:

- EU officials such as our Project Officer for purposes related to project's evaluation;
- EU agencies and other authorities for project's auditing purposes.

We would also be very happy if you gave us your consent to contact you in the future to ask you to participate in other project's activities (e.g. surveys, project events etc.) and also to inform you about the project's progress (e.g. by sending you a newsletter or similar messages).

How you can withdraw your consents?

You should know that you can withdraw your consent at any time by communicating by email with the responsible persons listed previously. With regards to the informational messages and newsletters you can always opt out by simply clicking the link "Unsubscribe" or something similar included at the end of all the relevant messages.

9. **I hereby give my consent to Q-PLAN International for the processing of my personal data needed for:** *

*(Please tick the box below to confirm that you give us your consent for the respective subject. If the box left unticked mean that **you do not consent to the relevant subject.**)*

Check all that apply.

- My participation in the SKILLBILL Co-Creation Workshop to be held in June 2023.

8/1/23, 4:17 PM

Co-creation Workshop

10. **I hereby give my consent to Q-PLAN International for the processing of my personal data needed for:**

*(Please tick the boxes below to confirm that you give us your consent for the respective subject. Any boxes left unticked mean that **you do not consent to the relevant subject.**)*

Check all that apply.

- My participation in future activities of SKILLBILL
- Receiving newsletters and messages regarding SKILLBILL activities

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Google Forms

Annex III: Initial Official Invitation

Subject: Invitation to join the Stakeholder Joint Initiative of the EU funded project SKILLBILL

Dear Stakeholder,

We would like to invite you to join the Stakeholder Joint Initiative that is set up under the framework of the Horizon Europe funded SKILLBILL project, as an expert in the field of Renewable Energy System and/or Sustainable Fuel.

SKILLBILL aims at gaining interdisciplinary insights and expertise in the field of Renewable Energy Sources (RES), academic education and Vocational Educational Training (VET), while in parallel contributing to implementing the **European Green Deal**, the **Circular Economy Action Plan**, and Action plan on critical Raw material, and other policies on RES, helping Europe becoming **climate neutral by 2050**.

In this context, the project is establishing international multi-expertise structures for identifying improved skills among stakeholders and multi-level workers and lay a strong foundation for the much-needed acceleration of renewable energies deployment.

We are currently inviting select key stakeholders of the whole Quadruple Helix (academia, industries, public authorities, and citizens), actively involved in the RES sector to form the Joint Initiative of the project, with the aim to push the development of the next generation techs towards the sustainability and circularity, as well as to align priorities and needs of the whole RES value chain (from designers, tech providers, to end-users).

The mission of the Stakeholder Joint Initiative is to develop a large and strong foundation for the growth and acceleration of renewable energy development, with a view to a greener, more effective, and pervasive next generation of sustainable technology. Stakeholders will be involved to offer their transdisciplinary knowledge, sharing their views, past experiences and perceptions.

Four interdisciplinary Working Groups to discuss the technological and non-technological barriers for RES penetration will be created under the tasks of the Stakeholder Joint initiative. The main aim of working groups will be to translate the technological advantages into needed skills, addressing key needs in the RES market, which serve as a barrier for RES development.

You have been identified and selected as an important member of the RES ecosystem within your country and we would be delighted to have you on board!

We believe that your expertise and qualification can largely help SKILLBILL reaching its objectives to improve skills among stakeholders and multi-level workers and lay a strong foundation for the much-needed acceleration of renewable energies deployment.

The Stakeholder Joint Initiative will be formed via a co-creation workshop, which take place on the 14th of June 2023 at 11.00 CET.

CONTACT: info@skillbill-project.eu
VISIT: www.skillbill-project.eu

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If you are interested in participating to our Stakeholder Joint Initiative please register here!

During the co-creation workshop we will explain the details for the operation of the working groups, which formulate the Stakeholder Joint Initiative, and co-design the topics of their discussions in the future.

Further details on the Stakeholder Joint Initiative and on the Working Groups are fully described in the attached document along with additional info on the project.

Do not hesitate to contact us for any further clarification.

We are looking forward to hearing from you!

Sincerely,

Partner name

Organisation

CONTACT: info@skillbill-project.eu
VISIT: www.skillbill-project.eu

**Funded by
the European Union**

Working Groups Design and Operation

Working Group: Design and Operation

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ABBREVIATIONS

KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LHE	Lighthouse Expert
R&D	Research & Development
RES	Renewable Energy Systems
ToR	Terms of Reference
WG	Working Groups

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Working Group: Design and Operation

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Working Group: Design and Operation

1. Introduction

SKILLBILL project aims at creating several pathways to induce the interest of targeted groups in Renewable Energy Systems (RES) besides their initial level of education and their working position. In order to increase soft and hard skills of potential users and stakeholders and to develop interest in the topic of RES, SKILLBILL will create tools and learning modules, with ultimate goal to increase the awareness of RES and fight against lack of information, bad quality materia, fake news, gender gap and the phenomenon of functional illiteracy, after having mapped knowledge gap.

In this context SKILLBILL entails the formation of 4 interdisciplinary **Working Groups** (WG) with the Quadruple Helix involvement to discuss on technological and non-technological barriers for RES penetration , to push the development of the next generation technologies towards sustainability and circularity, and lastly to align priorities and needs in the whole energy value chain. The Working Groups **mission is** to produce practical knowledge and policy recommendations translating knowledge gaps into training skills to support the developments of RES.

This document titled “**Working Group Design and Operation**”, has been elaborated as a report, providing an overview of context and rationale, and describing the approach to be followed for the development and the operation of the WGs.

This report is comprised of the following sections:

- **The introduction** gives an overview of the main role and purpose of the Working Groups and within the wider context of establishing networks of energy community and value chain actors. Finally, it briefly describes the various sections of the report.
- **Stakeholder Engagement** describes the categories of the possible working groups members and their indicative characteristics, along with the engagement process in order to form the WGs.
- **Selection Process** of the members with specific **selection criteria** presents the frame according to which the members will be selected, under specific criteria.
- **Number and thematic focus of WG** outlines the structure and the objectives the WG, along with the **expected outcomes** in the course of the project
- **Expected Outcomes** describe the main results, which are expected from the WGs
- **Management and Coordination of the WG** describes the involved partners and their specific role, along with contact details, and to whom the WG members could refer to, in case of any clarification.
- **Operational Model** summarizes the timeline, the specific activities, in which WGs members will participate in the frame of SKILLBILL project.
- **Monitoring Framework and Results’ Assessment** outlines the monitoring, evaluation and reporting mechanisms in place to ensure the effective performance of the WGs in relations to the project objectives and related KPIs

Working Group: Design and Operation

2. Stakeholder Invitation, Approach & Engagement

The initial recruitment of members for the WGs will be implemented with the support of the SKILLBILL partners that reach out to their networks of relevant stakeholders in the field of renewables and the energy value chain. To be more specific the following table presents the profile of potential stakeholders:

Table 1. Categories of stakeholders

Scientific Community	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Educational Institutions Researchers & Research Organisations Professors Students R&D units in private companies Experts on the field
Policy Makers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> EU institutions (European Commission) National and Local Public Authorities International Policy Makers
Energy Associations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> National Energy Associations Bioenergy Associations Energy Communities Energy Clusters
Industry Technology Providers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Hydropower Industry Solar Power Industry Wind Energy Industry Geothermal Energy Industry Biomass Energy Industry Hydrogen Industry
SMEs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> RES Experts Engineers Workers RES designers Installers
Potential Investors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Investors active in the fields of energy Network operators and distributors Green Financing Providers

Working Group: Design and Operation

	Business Angels
	Venture Capitalists

The next table outlines the guidelines for partners to establish the contact with stakeholders as well as principles for fostering their inclusion and effective engagement. The first contact with WG members and their invitation to join the WGs will be implemented through dedicated communication materials developed by Q-PLAN to facilitate the initial approach. A co-creation workshop will be organized in order to validate and co-define the Working Groups operation, also defining the communication context between the members of working groups, the partnership and of the SKILLBILL Advisory Board Members. In particular, through a registration form, all potential members of the Working Groups will be asked to give their consent in order to be contacted by the Working Group Manager, as all Working Groups will be managed by the WG Manager, that is Q-PLAN International, who will be responsible to keep track of WG activities, support good operation of WGs, support communication between WG members and collaborate with a dedicated Lighthouse Expert, who will be expert on the field of each WG thematic. To engage the Stakeholders in the different Working Groups, the following steps will be followed:

Table 2. Steps for stakeholder Engagement

Step	Who	Material	When
Identification and communication with potential members	Partners	Communication pack: Incl. info for SKILLBILL, SKILLBILL leaflet, online registration form for the co-creation workshop	May 2023
Co-creation Workshop	Q-PLAN	Boards prepared on Mirò, Mural or other user-friendly co-creation software	June 2023
Official Invitation to potential members	Q-PLAN	ToR, Declaration of Acceptance in electronic format (e.g. google form), Subject Form	September 2023
Acceptance engagement of	Members of WG	Officially sign a Declaration of Acceptance	September 2023

It is important to note that only under a signed declaration of acceptance is a stakeholder officially accepted as a WG member..

Although members of the WGs may be invited because of their affiliations with key organizations, they serve in their **individual capacity** to represent the interests and views of their stakeholder

Working Group: Design and Operation

communities. Members of the WGs may not delegate another person to carry out the role expected from them or be replaced by any other person in all WGs activities (meetings).

A remuneration is foreseen for the Working Group members in the maximum amount of 1000€ (for all 3 years of project duration). To receive the fee, the WG member has to participate in all working group meetings (4 meetings in total), and to issue an invoice that is addressed to SKILLBILL Coordinator, including the elements stated below:

AzzeroCO2, Via Genova 23, 00184 Roma; Italy

VAT Number

Fiscal Authority

Justification: Participation in the [Name of the Working Group] Working Group Meetings under SKILLBILL Project (CON. NO. 101075587)/Horizon Europe

The contribution of WG members could also be on a **pro bono basis**. Moreover, participation in the WGs is entirely voluntary. There will be no adverse consequences if a WG member decides not to participate or to withdraw at any stage. In fact, WG members may withdraw their participation at any time by informing the WG Manager (Q-PLAN INTERNATIONAL). They may also request for their data to be withdrawn without giving any reason and without prejudice. Anonymous data already collected will be used because this information cannot be traced back to a specific person, but no further data or input will be collected, nor any other procedure will be carried out in relation to the specific member. In case of withdrawal from WG activities or non-show to a WG meeting, the member acknowledges the rule to receive no fee foreseen. In case of withdrawal, the Member is encouraged to offer a substitute person with relevant interest in the Working Group activities/discussions to assure the flow of WG work and success of results.

3. Selection Process & Selection Criteria

Consortium partners are responsible for the selection of stakeholders included in the WG set-up. The stakeholders will be contacts deriving from their existing networks. It is important to identify the most appropriate persons based on specific criteria and expertise. A common process should be followed as presented in the figure below:

Figure 1. Selection Process

The criteria applied for selecting the members of the WGs, in line with the mission and expected structure of each Working Group, capture a broad range of dimensions regarding the characteristics of stakeholders necessary for their meaningful participation in WG activities. Along these lines, the following table summarises selection criteria and justification for their inclusion.

Table 3: Selection criteria and rationale for criteria inclusion

No.	Selection criterion	Rationale for criterion inclusion
1	Expertise	The potential Working Groups' members should have expertise in the thematic of each focus group, focusing in renewable energy sector and education in techs fields and/or environment.
2	Interest	Stakeholders with high interest in the energy sector and particularly in renewable energy systems will ensure that they are driven to participate and help the project produce meaningful results with significant added value for RES users.
3	Availability	Stakeholders that have the available time required to participate will enable partners to smoothly organise and execute project activities with higher participation rates that will result in higher targets reached.
4	Relevance	The relevance of stakeholders to the project's scope and objectives is necessary to keep activities of the WG focused and to ensure that WG members can effectively contribute to the production of accordingly relevant project outputs.
5	Appropriateness	The consortium will make sure that members selected to participate in the WG are appropriate to their scope thus avoiding conflicts of interest or subjecting them in activities that may cause unnecessary inconvenience.

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No.	Selection criterion	Rationale for criterion inclusion
6	Representativeness	A balanced representation of perspectives within and across stakeholder groups is key for the WGs to collect the representative insights required to inform design, development and fine-tuning of training needs.
7	Willingness	Motivated stakeholders willing to contribute with their knowledge and experience will promote success of WG activities and will be more prone to help disseminate the project's tools and knowledge, facilitating exploitation and sustainability.
8	Gender	The recruitment of each Working Group will seek to keep a gender balance.

4. Number and thematic focus of WG

The Working Groups are set up and operate as a liaison structure for various stakeholders and experts to share their knowledge and expertise with the SKILLBILL project in key deployment stages.

4.1 Number of WG

During the course of the project four (4) separate working groups will be created, which will operate in parallel, in terms of timeframe, and will focus on different thematics. Each WG will involve 6-8 members deriving from different backgrounds thus offering a mixture of stakeholders' expertise and skills.

4.2 Thematic Focus of WG

The SKILLBILL partners have co-decided the thematic focuses of each Working Groups, voting for the best categorisation, so the results came up to the following thematic for each working group:

Table 4. Thematic Focus of each WG

	<p>Sustainable and Renewable Electricity & Skills Gap impacting its full deployment potential</p>	<p>Power to grid and market of electricity: characteristics of power grid, variability of energy mix, operation of electricity market, incentive to promote the installation of renewable energy technologies for power generation.</p> <p>VRE¹ technologies: PV² systems (small and large scale), wind turbines, interaction with the grid</p>
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¹ VRE: Variable Renewable Energy

² PV: Photovoltaic

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		<p>Dispatchable Renewable Energy Technologies: Hydroelectric, CSP³, linear collectors, geothermal and WHR⁴, Organic Rankine Cycle</p>
	<p>Sustainable Mobility & Skills Gap impacting its full deployment potential</p>	<p>Road Transport: Fuels and emissions of road vehicles (light and heavy), electric vehicles, hydrogen cars, biofuels (generation and distribution and storage), fast chargers for electric vehicles</p> <p>Air transport: Sustainable Aviation fuels, Hydrogen aircraft, Electric Aircraft</p> <p>Maritime transport: carbon footprint of maritime transportation, sustainable marine fuels</p>
	<p>Sustainable and Renewable Heat & Skills Gap impacting its full deployment potential</p>	<p>Renewable heat technologies: geothermal, bioenergy (incl. CHP⁴), WHR⁵, electrical heating and district heating</p> <p>Sustainable heat in built environment: Insulation, heat pumps, solar energy, wood pellet, distinct heating and heat storage</p> <p>Industrial renewable heat</p>
	<p>Sustainable and Renewable Fuels & Skills Gap impacting its full deployment potential</p>	<p>Biofuels processes (gasification, syngas⁶, biooils / upgrading, biomass production and pre-treatment)</p> <p>Waste to Fuels, waste oils, HVO⁷, pyrolysis of biomass / gasification, biowaste to biogas</p> <p>Renewable energy to chemicals and fuels (power to hydrogen, methane, ammonia, syngas process)</p>

³ CSP: Concentrated Solar Power

⁴ CHP: Combined Heat and Power

⁵ WHR: Waste Heat Recovery

⁶ Syngas: Synthesis gas, is a mixture of hydrogen and carbon monoxide

⁷ HVO: Hydrotreated Vegetable Oil

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5. Aim and expected outcomes

The aim of the WGs is to provide knowledge and expertise on key developments and challenges that threaten the effective decarbonisation of the energy sector and the deployment of renewable energy innovations. In this context, the 4 SKILL BILL WGs are designed to engage with **stakeholders who address skills gaps and labour market shortages and develop concrete solutions and actions that raise awareness and the level of education among academia, industry, decision-makers and civil society, and improve skills that are required to foster future-proof labour markets, in university education and research, as well as in innovation and the formulation of better policies and regulation that emphasizes, amongst others, bridging the gender gap.**

To this end, each group will be comprised of an interdisciplinary team, including experts that can help translate technological advances into new education/training needs. As such, the outputs of each group will encompass:

- (i) solutions for driving the development of skills that will help implement sustainable renewable energy and fuel techs;
- (ii) meaningful recommendations for changes in regulation that shape a favourable environment for actors driving the energy transition towards net-zero.
- (iii) guidelines for education / training programmes to facilitate skilling, reskilling and upskilling.

The main theme of all four Working Groups is the identification of new jobs that existing and next generations of renewable energy and fuel technologies will be creating as well as skills required for these jobs.

The goals of the WGs is:

- (i) to inform industries on future needs to drive the RES development
- (ii) provide suggestions for policy makers on how to improve the regulatory frameworks;
- (iii) to translate the technological advances into new education / training needs.

To fulfil their role, it is envisaged that each WG during the implementation of SKILL BILL will operate through semestrial online meetings, that will be facilitated by a Lighthouse Expert. The online meetings will also use digital means (miro, online questionnaires, online forms etc) to capture the members' ideas, suggestions and priorities. To animate each Working Group in a direct and structured exchange of ideas, a common chat may be created to share information and views on the targeted thematic

6. Operational Model

6.1 Meetings and Timeline

The table below presents an initial timeline of critical steps for the operation of the WGs that will be further developed and enriched by the results of the Co-Creation Workshop in terms of performance monitoring and impact assessment. Each WG will meet on a semestrial basis online, in terms of online meeting with less than 2 hours durations. The facilitation of meetings will be done by a selected Lighthouse expert (see 6.3), who will set the goal of each meeting and propose the theme of each meeting's discussion. Also, during the course of the project, two (2) Mobilizations and Mutual Learning Workshops are foreseen - with the estimated their duration of 2-3 hours, where the Working

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Groups' Members will be invited to participate. The MMLs aim to collect suggestions, recommendations and ideas for further improving the outputs of the working groups. The semestrial meeting of the Working Groups are going to feed the first MML, which results will feed the plenary meeting. After all, the second MML will be fed by the plenary meeting in order to improve the recommendations and outputs of the Working Groups. In M24 (August 2024) a report of the outputs and results along with their assessment with a specific indicator will be included in D2.3: Actionable results from working groups and MML workshop - Initial Version. An update of the rest of the meetings as well as the outcomes of MML will be included in D2.3: Actionable Results from working groups and MML workshop – Final Version.

Figure 2. Timeplan of 4WGs and MML Workshops

Table 1. WGs topics of discussion as per action list

1st Meeting M15 Nov 2023	Topic: Solutions for driving the development and adoption of renewable electricity & Skills Gap impacting its full deployment potential Expected Recommendations 1-2	Topic: Solutions for driving the development and adoption of sustainable mobility & Skills Gap impacting its full deployment potential Expected Recommendations 1-2	Topic: Solutions for driving the development and adoption of renewable heat & Skills Gap impacting its full deployment potential Expected Recommendations 1-2	Topic: Solutions for driving the development and adoption of renewable fuels and biofuels & Skills Gap impacting its full deployment potential Expected Recommendations 1-2
2nd Meeting M21 May 2024	Topic: Directions for regulatory shifts to shape favourable environment for sustainable renewable electricity	Topic: Directions for regulatory shifts to shape favourable environment for sustainable mobility & Skills Gap	Topic: Directions for regulatory shifts to shape favourable environment for renewable heat & Skills Gap impacting	Topic: Directions for regulatory shifts to shape favourable environment for renewable fuels and biofuels & Skills Gap

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	& Skills Gap impacting its full deployment potential diffusion Expected Recommendations 1-2	impacting its full deployment potential diffusion Expected Recommendations 1-2	its full deployment potential diffusion Expected Recommendations 1-2	impacting its full deployment potential diffusion Expected Recommendations 1-2
3rd Meeting M27 Nov 2024	Topic: Guidelines for educational /training programs to facilitate skilling reskilling upskilling in renewable Electricity & Skills Gap impacting its full deployment potential Expected Recommendations: 1-2	Topic: Guidelines for educational /training programs to facilitate skilling reskilling upskilling in sustainable mobility & Skills Gap impacting its full deployment potential Expected Recommendations: 1-2	Topic: Guidelines for educational /training programs to facilitate skilling reskilling upskilling in renewable heat & Skills Gap impacting its full deployment potential Expected Recommendations: 1-2	Topic: Guidelines for educational /training programs to facilitate skilling reskilling upskilling renewable fuels and biofuels & Skills Gap impacting its full deployment potential Expected Recommendations: 1-2
Plenary M33 May 2025	Topic: Identify new jobs and skills required in RES Translate technological advantages into educational/training needs in RES			

6.2 WG Manager

The WG Manager (Q-PLAN INTERNATIONAL), with the administrative role, will handle communications and interactions with WGs and its members and monitor their engagement to ensure smooth operation and meaningful results. For this purpose, a WG member Matrix (Annex I) has been developed to keep track of participation in activities and to ensure meaningful, results oriented interaction whilst a balanced engagement of all WG members is achieved. WG Manager will create a communication path (chat) for fast communication between the members and easy exchange of ideas.

The Stakeholder Matrix is created as a dedicated tool to keep track and monitor the engagement of WG members in project activities. The Stakeholder Matrix will be updated by the WG manager after every activity with a view to monitoring and documenting the results of the project in this respect and, if necessary, take action to ensure the effectiveness of the mechanism.

The Working Group Manager will be responsible for the organisation of the meeting, (agenda, invitations) and also will be the main contact point for any inquiry, complaint or concern about any aspect of the experience and a member of the WGs.

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6.3 Lighthouse Expert

During the course of the project four (4) lighthouse experts (LHE) will coordinate and support the working groups. LHEs are persons with technical expertise in each WG thematic focus. The LHE, based on the topic of each meeting will prepare questions and main focus of discussion of each meeting, will chair and facilitate the discussion, will propose interaction solutions (slido, post-it, voting etc) in order to keep the participation of members active and engaging. Moreover, the LHE will encourage fast communication between the members through a chosen tool. Last but not least, the LHE will be responsible for writing a brief report on the results of each meeting. The brief report will be delivered on a given template (Annex 8.3), that will be created by the WG Manager (Q-PLAN), also attaching the meeting agenda (Annex 8.2), participant list and basic outcomes. The most important task to derive from the WG meeting are 20 recommendations to be collected at the end of all WG meetings.

6.4 Sustain the WGs

WGs will settle cooperation initiatives that may sustain their discussions beyond the project duration. Being four already formulated networks, the WGs may voluntarily be expanded also involving other members on a pro bono basis if the members wish to expand the WG lifespan. The 4 Working Groups may work in parallel with SKILLBILL Master to feed academia with important information deriving directly from the market/ stakeholders, keeping up with tech progress, and future skills required. If members decide to go forward with the Working Groups, they should announce it widely and continue communicating with the dedicated communication tool (chat) to make sure that all impacted teams are informed and bought into the initiative, and to ask for frequent input. A charter document is recommended to be created based on this Design document.

7. Monitoring Framework, reporting and assessment

In the framework adopted in this operation model for WGs, monitoring and evaluation are not disconnected activities with the WG members. The activities and generated results are rather to be seen on a continuum and contribute to the same process. They are linked together through “result-oriented monitoring”, which provides an overall framework reflecting the WG concept. The Co-Creation Workshop scheduled for June 2023 (M10) with the support of all partners, will enable us to engage in a series of interdisciplinary meetings with key stakeholders to co-define key aspects of gaps and needs in training regarding the RES development and adoption.

7.1 Monitoring Framework

WG Manager (Q-PLAN INTERNATIONAL) will monitor the following indicators:

1. Number of members per WG (signed consent forms)
2. Number of meetings performed
3. Number of attendees in each meeting
4. Policy Recommendations developed

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7.2 Reporting and assessment

LHE is tasked to provide a report to the WG Manager (Q-PLAN INTERNATIONAL), which will include the summarization of the meeting, the results on solutions, regulatory shifts and education guidelines, as derived during the WG meetings exchange, and the outcomes which came up during the discussion. The WG Manager (Q-PLAN INTERNATIONAL) will collect all meeting reports along with photos of the meeting and summarize them, in order to describe their activities, and progress towards the expected results and the generated recommendations within the SKILLBILL project. All reports will be the basis for the D2.3 - Actionable results from the Working Groups and MML workshops, due in M24 and updated with MML results in M36. As a tool for actively reporting on stakeholders reached KPI, the stakeholders will be asked to prioritize the final 20 recommendations lighted out from the Working Groups meetings, from the most important to the least important in order to capture their interest and also their view.

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8. Annexes

8.1 WG members matrix

SKILLBILL WG Stakeholder Matrix													
Contact Details			Anonymized Details			Demographics			Project Meetings				Additional Info
Name of contact person	Email address of contact person	Proposed by partner (Please Select)	Organisation Name	Stakeholder Group (Please Select)	Expertise in RES (Please select)	Country	Age of contact person (Please Select)	Gender of contact person (Please Select)	1st Meeting	2nd Meeting	3rd Meeting	Primary Meeting	Comments

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8.2 Indicative Working Group Meeting Agenda

Time	Topic
Welcome	
5'	Start of Meeting - Welcome
10'	Tour de la table
15'	Scope of the meeting - Presentation of the topic
Session 1: Discussion of the topic	
15'	Insights into the needs and barriers of the topic
15'	Brainstorming and exchange
Session 2: Recommendations	
15'	Discussion and co-creation of recommendations
15'	Elaboration of Recommendations
Meeting Conclusion	
15'	Conclusion and wrap-up of the meeting

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8.3 Indicative Reporting Template of the Working Group Meeting

General Information

Organizational Details

Table 1. Details of the Meeting

Organisational Details and Achievements	Metrics and Explanation
Working Group Thematic Focus	
No of Meeting	
Date of Meeting	
Platform / Digital tools used	
No of Participants	
Duration of Meeting (hours)	
Name of Lighthouse Expert	
Report Author	
No of recommendations created	

Table 2. List of Participants

Participants		
	Full Name of Participant	Membership
1	xx	LHE
2	xx	Consortium
		Working Groups Member

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	Absent Working Group Members	

Topic of Discussion

Please describe (1 paragraph of 10 - 15 lines) the scope and the topic covered during the meeting.

Overview of the Meeting

Please describe (1 paragraph of 10 - 15 lines) the approach followed to prepare and organise the meeting, highlighting and briefly explaining the main activities that took place. Mention any preparatory material that you may have used as well! Also report on other communication done prior to the meeting in order to activate the WG members (eg common chat discussion, prioritisation of recommendations, voting procedures etc)

Outcomes and recommendations

Please provide a structured summary of the results stemming from your working group meeting (in tabular format when possible as suggested) which can be used directly as input for the deliverable.

Recommendations

Please provide an overview of the recommendations presented or identified in the meeting, indicating their ranking and providing some basic info and explanation behind them (short text in bullets).

Table 3. Recommendations of the Meeting

Rank	Recommendation	Brief Description
1		
2		
3		
4		
5		

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○ **Key Insights stemming from the discussions**

Complete this section by presenting and discussing any key take away remarks, feedback or insights that may have emerged from the discussions addressing the topics provided in the agenda. Emphasise common success factors and barriers for replication identified during the discussions (2 paragraphs max).

● **Concluding remarks and Sum up**

Process provide any closing remarks (1 paragraph of 4 – 5 lines) from the meeting, addressing the following indicative questions:

- Were participants informed about future WG activities?
- Did they seem to be willing to participate in these activities?
- Overall, did the meeting succeed in its objectives?

Please sum up the insights of the discussion regarding the development of the recommendations. based on the feedback received during the meeting (2 paragraphs).

The project

SKILLBILL's overall objective is to develop a large and strong foundation for the growth and acceleration of renewable energy's deployment, thanks to engaging with stakeholders of the whole chain, diffusing scientific culture and skilling multi-level workers. The basic idea underlying the project is that the knowledge should be diffused at several different levels and qualitatively appropriate both to train the adequate number of workers and to increase RES awareness and to reach a more social and inclusive Europe. The project aims at creating several pathways to induce target groups to get interested or involved in RES besides their initial level of education and their working position. It's important, beside the creation of instruments for the upskilling and reskilling of workers, technician and designers, to have awareness modules for unspecific public in order to fight against lack of information, bad quality material, gender gap and the phenomenon of functional illiteracy: it is widely documented that lifelong suitable learning process is the fundamental driver to support the development, maintenance and update of skills. Thus, SKILLBILL proposes concrete actions to accelerate the deployment of renewable energy at different levels to analyse and involve all the interested parts in open discussion using adequate language; create several different pathways to increase skills after having mapped knowledge gap and without gender prejudice; develop and implement innovative learning method; and evaluate the work performed.

Coordinator: **AZZERO CO2 SRL (AzzeroCO2)**

	PARTNER	SHORT NAME
	AZZERO CO2 SRL	AzzeroCO2
	Q-PLAN INTERNATIONAL ADVISORS PC	Q-PLAN
	WHITE RESEARCH SPRL	WR
	UNIVERSITA DEGLI STUDI DELLA TUSCIA	UNITUS
	UNIVERSIDAD DE SEVILLA	USE
	METROPOLIA AMMATTIKORKEAKOULU OY	METROPOLIA
	UNIVERSITEIT UTRECHT	UU
	EUROPEAN RENEWABLE ENERGIES FEDERATION	EREF
	SINERGIE SOC CONS ARL	SINERGIE
	PEDAL CONSULTING SRO	PC

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Annex V: Terms of Reference

Working Groups

Terms of References

Q-PLAN INTERNATIONAL

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ABBREVIATIONS

LHE	Lighthouse Expert
RES	Renewable Energy Systems
ToR	Terms of References
WG	Working Groups
STEM	Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation

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1. Introduction

You have been invited to the **SKILLBILL Working Groups** (WG). The current document outlines the Terms of Reference (ToR) that will help you understand the benefits participating in Working Groups and what your involvement is all about, before you decide to participate. Please take time to carefully read this document and ask for any clarifications you may have, by sending your question to the Working Group Manager, Q-PLAN (under Chapter 6-Contact Point).

1.1 SKILLBILL in a nutshell

The transition to a carbon-free energy system is a societal challenge not just a technical problem. The complexity of energy policy and the issues that policymakers deal with are not necessarily those that energy consumers face. The basic idea underlying the project is that knowledge should be diffused at different levels, qualitatively appropriate both to train an adequate number of workers and to increase awareness in Renewable Energy Systems (RES), reaching a more social and inclusive Europe. With that in mind, SKILLBILL aims to pave the way to **different forms of training and education** in order to meet new skills requirements in the RES field as well as induce citizens and stakeholders to get **interested or involved in RES** regardless of their level of education, their working position and their gender. The technological RES potential can be reached by increasing hard and soft skills of potential users and stakeholders, developing interest in the topic and having clear and appropriate approaches, such as tools and learning modules using suitable language. SKILLBILL recognizes the need for lifelong learning opportunities on RES, in order to fight functional illiteracy and to maintain and update skills of workers, technicians and designers, on the field, to promote renewable energy systems. Moreover, SKILLBILL acknowledges the importance of raising awareness of the general public, so as to achieve wider RES deployment.

1.2 Goal and Scope of SKILLBILL

The **ultimate goal** of SKILLBILL is to contribute to the implementation of the European Green Deal priorities, Circular Economy Action Plan and the Action Plan on Critical Raw Materials and the achievement of a climate-neutral Europe by 2050.

SKILLBILL's **overall objective** is to develop a large and strong foundation for the growth and acceleration of renewable energy's deployment, thanks to engaging with stakeholders from the whole value chain, diffusing scientific culture and skilling multi-level workers.

Thus, SKILLBILL's **main objectives** are summarized below:

- Steer the development of a greener, more effective and pervasive next generation of sustainable technology
- Launch the point of reference for qualitative information on RES and promote the development of sustainable solutions (Green Portal)
- Develop an advanced permanent education program on RES at European level
- Develop a technical practical permanent Vocational Education Training program on RES
- Reduce gender gap in STEM
- Increase awareness, fighting against lack of information, bad quality of educational material and the phenomenon of functional illiteracy, therefore improving inclusiveness on RES

Working Groups: Terms of References

2. Purpose, Scope and Benefits

2.1 Purpose and Scope

The Working Groups (WG) are set-up and operated to share knowledge, expertise and give feedback to the consortium of the project on key topics in the energy sector. SKILLBILL sets-up 4 Working Groups under the thematic of

Table 1. Thematic Focus of Working Groups

Icon	Thematic Focus
	Sustainable and Renewable Electricity & Skills Gap impacting its full deployment potential
	Sustainable Mobility & Skills Gap impacting its full deployment potential
	Sustainable and Renewable Heat & Skills Gap impacting its full deployment potential
	Sustainable and Renewable Fuels & Skills Gap impacting its full deployment potential

Each Working Group will involve **6-8 members** that are stakeholders from the whole value chain of the respective RES sector. The role of the WG members in the context of the project may be summed up as follows:

Provide feedback and insights for the development process of renewable energy's innovations, by participating in such discussions and propose concrete actions to incentivise and expedite the development and the adoption of sustainable renewable energy and fuel technologies.

Produce practical knowledge and policy recommendations translating knowledge gap into training skills to support the developments of RES

As the Working Groups outputs are focused on policy recommendations and considering the scope of SKILLBILL project they could be focus on actions that improve frameworks (at EU and national level) with regard to labour markets, skills, education etc.

To fulfil their role, it is envisaged that each WG during the course of the project will operate through semestrial online meetings, that will be facilitated by an expert that will act as a Lighthouse Expert on the relevant WG thematic. The online meetings will also use digital means (miro, online questionnaires, online forms etc) to capture the members' ideas, suggestions and priorities. To animate each working group in a direct and spontaneous exchange of ideas, a common chat may be created to share information and views on the targeted thematic.

2.2 Benefits

The project **provides several benefits** to its WG members, such as:

- **Networking opportunities and possibilities for new collaborations** arising from the participation in project events and workshops.
- **First-hand access to meaningful insights, knowledge and cutting-edge technologies** generated exclusively within the context of the project and its activities. This ensures they remain well-informed and adaptable in an ever-evolving industry
- Unique opportunity to **align the training schemes offered by SKILLBILL Project with the needs of their stakeholders** to ensure that they make the most out of its value propositions.
- **Shaping** the environment and future of next Generation of RES
- SKILL BILL under the frame of creating **synergies** with ongoing EU initiatives - in particular the "European Year of Skills" ¹but also recently launched policy files such as the net-zero industry act².
- **Contributing to Sustainable Development:** playing a direct role in promoting and accelerating the transition to renewable energy sources, contributing to global sustainable development goals.
- Enhancing **Visibility and Recognition** within industry via active involvement in working groups. It showcases the commitment to driving positive change and sustainable development in the renewable energy sector
- Enhancing **Project outcomes**, by collectively identifying and addressing skills needs, working groups enhance project outcomes in renewable energy development. A skilled and competent workforce is better equipped to drive successful and sustainable projects.
- **Access to Expertise:** Working groups bring together professionals, experts, and stakeholders from various backgrounds, providing access to a diverse pool of knowledge and skills. Participants can learn from one another and gain insights into best practices and innovative solutions.
- **Collaborative Problem-Solving:** Working groups foster collaborative problem-solving. Stakeholders can collectively identify skills gaps and needs in RES development, exploring practical strategies and actions to address them.

¹ European Year of Skills 2023, https://commission.europa.eu/strategy-and-policy/priorities-2019-2024/europe-fit-digital-age/european-year-skills-2023_en

² Net Zero Industry Act, Proposal for a regulation of the European Parliament, https://single-market-economy.ec.europa.eu/publications/net-zero-industry-act_en

Overall, participating in working groups focused on translating needs and gaps into skills required in RES development empowers stakeholders to be active agents of change, promoting a skilled and sustainable future for the renewable energy sector.

3. Terms of membership and Management

3.1 Rights and Obligations

WGs shall be composed of individuals coming from diverse backgrounds to offer a blend of expertise and perspectives that represent various stakeholder groups from the energy sector (such as producers, industries, distributors, academics, public authorities, consultants, NGOs etc.). These individuals will provide SKILLBILL with valuable knowledge and feedback to support the implementation of key project activities and studies, while the Working Groups members will gain insights and expand their networks. Along these lines, at the beginning of the project, 6-8 members for each one of the four thematic groups³ will be selected. The selection criteria are:

- Expertise in RES or Expertise in training and education in tech fields and/or environment, as well as in policy-making
- Interest for participation/involvement/partnership
- Availability to participate in Working Groups' activities
- Relevance to each thematic focus of each Working Group
- Appropriateness, in order to avoid conflicts that may arise
- Representativeness, within and across the stakeholder groups
- Willingness to contribute with their knowledge
- Gender in order to keep a gender balance within the Working Groups

Although members of the WG may be selected because of their affiliations with key organizations, they serve on the WG in their **individual capacity** to represent the interests and views of their stakeholder communities. **Members of the WG may not delegate another person to carry out the role expected from them** or be replaced by any other person without prior written agreement with the SKILLBILL consortium. Members of the WG are appointed for the entire duration of the respective task of the project (from 01st June 2023 to 31st August 2025). If due to job changes or attrition, a WG member loses links to important networks or constituencies, the consortium may decide to fill in this gap by appointing additional/substitute members.

Moreover, participation in the WG is entirely voluntary, but in order to be assigned as official members they will be asked to sign a Declaration of acceptance, taking into consideration of the Terms of Reference (this file), and accept the Informed Consent Form, following the GDPR rules.. There will be no adverse consequences if a WG member decides not to participate or to withdraw at any stage. In fact, WG members may withdraw their participation at any time by informing the Contact Person (see Section 6 of the current document). Respecting the GDPR rule, they may also request for their data to be withdrawn without giving a reason and without prejudice. Anonymous data already collected will be used because this information cannot be traced back to a specific person, but no further data or input will be collected, nor any other procedure will be carried out in relation to the specific member. In case of withdrawal, the Member is encouraged to offer a substitute person with

³ More details for the organisation of the groups are presented in [Design and Operation of Working Group File](#)

Working Groups: Terms of References

relevant interest in the Working Group activities/discussions to ease the flow of WG work and success of results.

3.2 Management

The WGs are administrative managed by the **Q-PLAN INTERNATIONAL** (see Section 6 below) which handles communications and interactions with the WGs' member ensuring that WG members are only addressed to by a unique Manager to avoid overload of communication, disperse of personal contact details and tasks confusion. Q-PLAN INTERNATIONAL will ensure that an action plan and all necessary briefings and material have been prepared before each WG meeting to assure flow of work.

A **lighthouse expert** (LHE) for each WG, assigned by the technical partners of the consortium, which are [EREF](#) and [AzzeroCO2](#), with the support of other partners if necessary will chair the semestrial meetings, coordinate the discussion and propose the topic. Having a technical background, the LHE will be responsible to report⁴ on the meeting's results and outcomes to a given template, prepared by the WG Manager. Moreover, the LHE will animate the discussion and communications to reach recommendations (facilitating the meetings and assuring that the meeting will come up with valuable knowledge and recommendations for the projects 5 by each working group) that will also be reported.

4. Planned Effort and Fees

4.1 Planned Effort

SKILLBILL foresees one meeting per six months at least for Working Groups members (in November of 2023, in May of 2024, in November of 2024 and in May of 2025), which means 3 meeting within the WGs and one plenary at the end with other WG, in order to cross fertilize ideas and improve the final outputs. The average duration of each meeting is estimated to be less than 2 hours. Also, during the course of the project, two (2) Mobilizations and Mutual Learning Workshops are foreseen, while their duration is estimated about 2-3 hours, to which the Working Groups' Member will be invited to participate. The semestrial meeting of the Working Groups are going to feed the first MML, which results will feed the plenary meeting. After all, the second MML will be fed by the plenary meeting in order to improve the recommendations and outputs of the Working Groups.

The invitation for the Working Groups Meetings will be addressed by the SKILLBILL responsible partner (Q-PLAN INTERNATIONAL) to the WGs members at least 30 days before the meeting. The invitation shall include a draft agenda and a storyboard along with expected outputs. The Working Groups may meet online. Other electronic means may be used if necessary to capture the WG Members' contributions, perceptions or suggestions.

⁴ The report will also include your anonymized data, following GDPR Rules, according to the Informed Consent Form that the members of Working Groups as part of the declaration of acceptance.

Working Groups: Terms of References

4.2 Remuneration

A remuneration fee is foreseen for the Working Group members in the maximum amount of 1000€ (for all 3 years of project duration). To receive the fee, the WG member has to participate in all working group meetings (4 meetings in total), and to issue an invoice that is addressed to SKILLBILL Coordinator, including the elements stated below:

AzzeroCO2, Via Genova 23, 00184 Roma; Italy

VAT Number

Fiscal Authority

Justification: Participation in the X Working Group Meetings under SKILLBILL Project (CON. NO. 101075587)/Horizon Europe

This amount will include eventual travel accommodation or any other costs incurred for participating in the WGs.

The fee may be reimbursed at the end of the WGs activities in one payment. The contribution of WG members could be also on a pro bono basis.

5. Operational Procedures

SKILLBILL foresees that each WG will meet on a semestrial basis. A month prior to the meeting, the WG members will receive the meeting agenda. The LHE will be the facilitator expected to animate the discussion and to inspire the members in contributing with their views and suggestions. A Member that wishes to further contribute with his/her suggestions is free to send recommendations, sources or other contributions via e-mail to the WG Manager or the LHE. The LHE will be the responsible person to sum up all information and experience shared (via the report). More details for the operation of the WG are included in the “Working Groups Design and Operation” document.

6. Contact Point

Any enquiry, complaint or concern about any aspect of your experience as a member of the Working Group can be addressed to the WG Manager, **Q-PLAN INTERNATIONAL** that oversees the set up and manages the Working Groups. The contact details of the responsible person are provided below:

Organisation: Q-PLAN INTERNATIONAL

Contact person: Andromachi Kalaouzi

Phone: +30 2310 257277, +30 2310 411 191

Email: kalaouzi@qplan-intl.gr

Working Groups: Terms of References

The project

SKILLBILL's overall objective is to develop a large and strong foundation for the growth and acceleration of renewable energy's deployment, thanks to engaging with stakeholders of the whole chain, diffusing scientific culture and skilling multi-level workers. The basic idea underlying the project is that the knowledge should be diffused at several different levels and qualitatively appropriate both to train the adequate number of workers and to increase RES awareness and to reach a more social and inclusive Europe. The project aims at creating several pathways to induce target groups to get interested or involved in RES besides their initial level of education and their working position. It's important, beside the creation of instruments for the upskilling and reskilling of workers, technician and designers, to have awareness modules for unspecific public in order to fight against lack of information, bad quality material, gender gap and the phenomenon of functional illiteracy: it is widely documented that lifelong suitable learning process is the fundamental driver to support the development, maintenance and update of skills. Thus, SKILLBILL proposes concrete actions to accelerate the deployment of renewable energy at different levels to analyse and involve all the interested parts in open discussion using adequate language; create several different pathways to increase skills after having mapped knowledge gap and without gender prejudice; develop and implement innovative learning method; and evaluate the work performed.

Coordinator: **AZZERO CO2 SRL (AzzeroCO2)**

	PARTNER	SHORT NAME
	AZZERO CO2 SRL	AzzeroCO2
	Q-PLAN INTERNATIONAL ADVISORS PC	Q-PLAN
	WHITE RESEARCH SPRL	WR
	UNIVERSITA DEGLI STUDI DELLA TUSCIA	UNITUS
	UNIVERSIDAD DE SEVILLA	USE
	METROPOLIA AMMATTIKORKEAKOULU OY	METROPOLIA
	UNIVERSITEIT UTRECHT	UU
	EUROPEAN RENEWABLE ENERGIES FEDERATION	EREF
	SINERGIE SOC CONS ARL	SINERGIE
	PEDAL CONSULTING SRO	PC

CONTACT US info@skillbill-project.eu VISIT www.skillbill-project.eu

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Annex VI: Declaration of Acceptance

INFORMED CONSENT FORM

Who we are:

We are [Q-PLAN INTERNATIONAL](#) and we are contacting you in the framework of SKILLBILL project funded by the European Union under the Horizon Europe Framework Programme for Research and Innovation. A detailed description on how SKILLBILL handles personal data is presented in the project's [Privacy Policy](#) available through the project's [web page](#).

Project:

SKILLBILL- Skill to Boost Innovation and professional fulfilment in a sustainable economy (GA Number 101075587).

Partner:

Organisation Name: Q-PLAN INTERNATIONAL

Address: 11, El. Venizelou st., PC 551 33, Kalamaria, Thessaloniki, Greece

Phone: +30 2310 257277 | +30 2310 411 191

E-mail: info@qplan-intl.gr

Responsible persons:

#	Role	Name	E-mail
1	SKILLBILL Project Manager	Dimitra Kyriakopoulou	kyriakopoulou@qplan-intl.gr
2	Working Group Manager	Andromachi Kalaouzi	kalaouzi@qplan-intl.gr
3	Data Protection Officer	Petros Papadionisiou	papadionisiou@qplan-intl.gr

What do we need from you?

We need you to participate in the SKILLBILL Working Groups and the related project activities (events, workshops, studies etc.) for the collection of useful information based on your experience and opinions that will be used for the development and acceptance of RES and educational and/or training needs in energy sector.

CONTACT: info@skillbill-project.eu

VISIT: www.skillbill-project.eu

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the European Union

Declaration of Acceptance

I, the undersigned, _____ certify that I have read and agree to abide by the SKILLBILL Working Group ~~Terms of Reference~~^[AK1].

I pledge that I will participate in the SKILLBILL Working Group, chosen below, in my individual capacity and as such I may not delegate another person to carry out the work or be replaced by any other person without prior written agreement with the SKILLBILL consortium. For all the above I would like to participate in the following Working Group:

- Sustainable and Renewable Electricity*
- Sustainable Mobility*
- Sustainable and Renewable Heat*
- Sustainable and Renewable Fuels*

I certify that no conflict of interests exists that could be considered as prejudicial to my independence in acting as a member of the SKILLBILL Working Group.

I undertake not to divulge any information given in the context of the work of the SKILLBILL, unless the SKILLBILL consortium agrees to release me from this obligation, and to respect the confidentiality requirements.

I declare to accept entirely and with no reservations my appointment as SKILLBILL Working Group member as described in the Terms of Reference.

I consent that any input or contribution I provide as member of the SKILLBILL Working Group may be used by the SKILLBILL consortium for reporting purposes or to align the educational design services and tools offered by SKILLBILL with the needs of final users to ensure that they make the most out of its value propositions.

I consent to the processing of my personal data needed for my participation in the SKILLBILL Working Group. A detailed description on how SKILLBILL handles personal data is presented in the project's [Privacy Policy](#) available through the project's web page at www.skillbill-project.eu.

Name of participant

Date

Signature | Place

CONTACT: info@skillbill-project.eu

VISIT: www.skillbill-project.eu

**Funded by
the European Union**

I hereby give my consent to the processing of my personal data needed for:

*(Please, tick the boxes below to confirm that you give us your consent for the respective subject. Any boxes left unticked mean that **you do not consent to the relevant subject.**)*

#	Consent Subject	Tick box
1	My participation in the SKILLBILL Working Group and activities related to development and acceptance of RES, alongside to education and training needs in energy sector	<input type="checkbox"/>
2	My participation in future activities of SKILLBILL	<input type="checkbox"/>
3	Receiving newsletters and messages regarding SKILLBILL activities	<input type="checkbox"/>

Name of participant

Date

Signature

CONTACT: info@skillbill-project.eu

VISIT: www.skillbill-project.eu

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the European Union**

To effectively carry out the activities of the Working Group, we will need to process some personal data of yours:

- Your contact details (full name, email);
- Some basic demographics (age, gender);
- Your professional info (organization, job position, field of expertise);
- Your education info
- Your experience and opinion on the subjects that will be discussed during our activities
- Videos and photos, captured during your participation in our events and activities

Why do we need your data & what will we do with them?

We need your data to contact you in order to plan and carry out the activities and events of the Working Groups in your field of interest and to resolve any ambiguities, questions and other issues that may arise after and as a result of the meetings. We also need to record your data to keep track of the activities and their results / outcomes. The project's deliverables that will be derived by these activities will not include your personal data or any other information that could identify you. Your personal data will remain on our written notes and records.

We will share your data with other two SKILLBILL project partners, AOCO2 (Coordinator) and EREF that will indicate the Lighthouse Experts. Moreover, your data will be shared with the Lighthouse Experts themselves, individuals assigned to lead the technical discussion of each Working Group, and to report on activities, recommendations and meetings held. We are also obliged to grant access to your data to:

- EU officials such as our Project Officer for purposes related to project's evaluation;
- EU agencies and other authorities for project's auditing purposes.

We would also be very happy if you gave us your consent to contact you in the future to ask you to participate in other project's activities (e.g. surveys, interviews, project events etc.) and also to inform you about the project's progress (e.g. by sending you a newsletter or similar messages).

How can you withdraw your consent?

You should know that you can withdraw your consent at any time by communicating either on the phone or by email with the responsible persons listed in the previous page. With regards to the informational messages and newsletters you can always opt out by simply clicking the link "Unsubscribe" or something similar included at the end of all the relevant messages.

CONTACT: info@skillbill-project.eu

VISIT: www.skillbill-project.eu

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the European Union**

Annex VII: Subject Form

Personal Data Involved

Request Detail

Request Reason / Justification

Name:

Signature:

Date:

Once completed, this form should be submitted via e-mail to Ms Andromachi Kalaouzi, kalaouzi@qplan-intl.gr

CONTACT: info@skillbill-project.eu

VISIT: www.skillbill-project.eu

**Funded by
the European Union**

Data Subject Request Form

This form should be used to submit a data subject request under the provisions of the European Union General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR).

Table 1. Submitter Details

Title:	
Name:	
Address:	

Type of Request

Please select the type of request you are making:

- Consent Withdrawal*
- Access request*
- Rectification of personal data*
- Erasure of personal data*
- Restriction of processing of personal data*
- Personal data portability request*
- Objection to processing of personal data*
- Request regarding automated decision making and profiling*

CONTACT: info@skillbill-project.eu

VISIT: www.skillbill-project.eu

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Text in red colour contains guidelines for adjusting this template and should be deleted.

Text included in < > and/or highlighted with yellow should be replaced with content that is suitable to the context of each activity & project as well as to the organisation seeking to obtain the consent.

Data Subject Request Form

You may delete the data referring to the Data Protection Officer if your organisation does not have one.

Contact¹

#	Role	Name	E-mail
1	SKILLBILL Project Manager	Dimitra Kyriakopoulou	kyriakopoulou@qplan-intl.gr
2	Working Group Manager	Andromachi Kalaouzi	kalaouzi@qplan-intl.gr
3	Data Protection Officer	Petros Papadionisiou	papadionisiou@qplan-intl.gr

¹ Rest assured that Q-PLAN will communicate your withdrawal from the working groups to A0CO2 and EREF

CONTACT: info@skillbill-project.eu

VISIT: www.skillbill-project.eu

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Annex VIII: Indicative Agenda of WG Meetings

Working Group Meeting

Indicative Agenda

Time	Topic
Welcome	
5'	Start of Meeting - Welcome
10'	Tour de la table
15'	Scope of the meeting - Presentation of the topic
Session 1: Discussion of the topic	
15'	Insights into the needs and barriers of the topic
15'	Brainstorming and exchange
Session 2: Recommendations	
15'	Discussion and co-creation of recommendations
15'	Elaboration of Recommendations
Meeting Conclusion	
15'	Conclusion and wrap-up of the meeting

Annex IX: Reporting Template for WG Meetings

WG X

Report of X Meeting

skillbill

SKILL TO BOOST INNOVATION & PROFESSIONAL FULFILLMENT IN A SUSTAINABLE ECONOMY

DD / MM / YYYY

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Working Group Meeting Report

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 1.3 **Overview of the Meeting**..... 4

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 2.1 **Recommendations**..... 4

 2.2 **Key Insights stemming from the discussions** 4

3. CONCLUDING REMARKS AND SUM UP5

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ABBREVIATIONS

TITLE	xxx

Working Group Meeting Report

1. General Information

1.1 Organisational Details

Table 1. Details of teh Meetng

Organisational Details and Achievements	Metrics and Explanation
Working Group Category ^[AK1]	
No of Meeting ^[AK2]	
Date of Meeting	
Platform / Digital tools used	
No of Participants ^[AK3]	
Duration of Meeting (hours)	
Name of Lighthouse Expert	
Report Authors	
No of recommendations created	

Table 2. List of Participants

Participants		
	Full Name of Participant	Membership
1	xx	LHE
2	xx	Consortium
		Working Groups Member
	Absent Working Group Members	

Working Group Meeting Report

1.2 Topic of Discussion

Please describe (1 paragraph of 10 -15 lines) the scope and the topic covered during the meeting.

1.3 Overview of the Meeting

Please describe (1 paragraph of 10 -15 lines) the approach followed to prepare and organise the meeting, highlighting and briefly explaining the main activities, that took place. Mention any preparatory material that you may have used as well! Also report on other communication done prior to the meeting in order to activate the WG members (eg common chat discussion, prioritisation of recommendations, voting procedures etc)

2. Outcomes and recommendation

Please provide a structured summary of the results stemming from your working group meeting (in tabular format when possible as suggested) which can be used directly as input for the deliverable.

2.1 Recommendations

Please provide an overview of the recommendations presented or identified in the meeting, indicating their ranking and providing some basic info and explanation behind them (short text in bullets).

Table 3. Recommendations of the Meeting

Rank	Recommendation	Brief Description
1		
2		
3		
4		
5		

2.2 Key Insights stemming from the discussions

Complete this section by presenting and discussing any key take away remarks, feedback or insights that may have emerged from the discussions addressing the topics provided in the agenda. Emphasise common success factors and barriers for replication identified during the discussions (2 – 3 paragraphs max).

Working Group Meeting Report

3. Concluding remarks and Sum up

Process provide any closing remarks (1 paragraph of 4 – 5 lines) from the meeting, addressing the following indicative questions:

- Were participants informed about future MAP activities?
- Did they seem to be willing to participate in these activities?
- Overall, did the meeting succeed in its objectives?

Please sum up the insights of the discussion regarding the development of the recommendations. based on the feedback received during the workshop (2 paragraphs).

Agenda

Time (CET)	Topic
Welcome	
11:00 – 11:05	Start of Workshop – Welcome
11:05 – 11:15	Tour de la table
11.15 – 11.25	Introduction to SKILLBILL Project – Presentation of the Topic
11:25 – 11:30	Icebreaker – Online tools explanation
Session 1: Operation of the Working Groups	
11:30 – 11:50	Working Groups Insights and Operational Model
11:50 – 12:00	Feedback on operational model by the participants - Discussion
12:00 – 12:15	Break
Session 2: Thematic Focus Co-creation	
12:15 – 12:30	Timeline and expected outcomes by the working groups
12:30 – 13:40	Co-creation session on the topics of discussion of each working group [Breakout Rooms and Plenary Session] – presentation of results
13:40 – 13:55	Choose KPIs
Meeting Conclusion	
13:55 – 14:00	Highlights – Closing

CONTACT US info@skillbill-project.eu **VISIT** www.skillbill-project.eu

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Annex XII: Photos of the co-creation workshop

Annex XIII: Presentations for the co-creation workshop

Co-creation Workshop
Stakeholder Joint Initiative

Wednesday, 14th of June 2023

Q-PLAN INTERNATIONAL

PARTNERS

AzzeroCO, Q-PLAN INTERNATIONAL, WHITE, UNIVERSITÀ TUSCIA, Metropolia University of Applied Sciences, Utrecht University, EREF, SINERGIE, PEDAL CONSULTING

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Funded by the European Union

Welcome!

Where the idea comes to life!

AzzeroCO, Q-PLAN INTERNATIONAL, WHITE, UNIVERSITÀ TUSCIA, Metropolia University of Applied Sciences, Utrecht University, EREF, SINERGIE, PEDAL CONSULTING

Keep your phones close and unleash your creativity during our co-creation workshop!

PARTNERS

Tour de la table

“Unlock the Power of Connection”

Let's Begin by Introducing Ourselves!

PARTNERS

Let us introduce ourselves

www.qplan-intl.gr

11 El. Venizelou str, 55133, Kalamaria, Greece

+30 2310 411 191

info@qplan-intl.gr

Dimitra Kyriakopoulou
 Project Manager
 Urban & Regional Planning and
 Innovation (MSc)
kyriakopoulou@qplan-intl.gr

Andromachi Kalaouzi
 Project Consultant
 Environmental Engineer (MSc)
kalaouzi@qplan-intl.gr

PARTNERS

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Q-PLAN INTERNATIONAL ADVISORS

Was established in 2000

We focus mainly on International projects & Studies, Management Systems and Funding programs

Is located in Thessaloniki

>50
 EU RTDI Projects & Studies since 2003

>30
 In-house Consultants & extensive network of Experts across the EU and beyond

>500
 Clients (SMEs, PUBLIC AUTHORITIES, etc.)

ISO 9001
 Certified for all our activities

Introduce yourself, ignite collaboration and empower your collective potential

miro

skillbill

PARTNERS

- AzzeroCO2
- Q-PLAN INTERNATIONAL
- WHITE
- UNIVERSITÀ DI TUSCIA
- Metropolia University of Applied Sciences
- Utrecht University
- EREF
- SINERGIE
- PEDAL CONSULTING

Agenda

1. Introduction to SKILLBILL
2. The workshop at a glance
3. Operation of the Working Groups
4. 1st Co-creation session – Suggestions on Operational Model
5. Meetings of Working Groups
6. 2nd Co-creation Session – Meeting Topics

Introduction to SKILLBILL

“Skill to Boost Innovation and professional fulfillment in a sustainable economy”

PARTNERS

SKILLBILL identity

Work programme	Horizon Europe
Type of Action	HORIZON Coordination and Support Actions (CSA)
Duration	36 Months From Sep 2022 to Aug 2025
Funding Authority	CINEA European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency
Budget	2,493,640.00 €
EC contribution	2,493,640.00 €
Coordinator	AzeroCO ₂ climate in our hands
No of partners	10 partners from 7 countries

Consortium as a whole

Academic Institution	4 Universities
Training	1 VET provider
Advisors	4 Business Advisors
Policy Authorities	1 Policy Federation

The problem to be addressed

- How to bridge the knowledge gap between poor-skilled employees and training materials ?
- How to boost the training in the renewable energy and renewable fuel technology (traditional training vs innovative training) ?
- How to spread the knowledge at different levels in an innovative way ?
- How to involve women in technology innovation and research ?

PARTNERS

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What SKILLBILL aims to achieve

Skilling | Reskilling | Upskilling

1. Steer the next generation of RES technologies
2. Create a point of reference for qualitative material
3. Advance the permanent education programs on RES
4. Design technical permanent VET programs
5. Reduce gender gap in STEM

PARTNERS

Main Activities – Expected Results

Stakeholder Joint Initiative

4 working Groups

- Sustainable and Renewable Electricity
- Sustainable Mobility
- Sustainable and Renewable Heat
- Sustainable and Renewable Fuels

Green Portal

Scan Here

skillbill-greenportal.eu

Main Activities – Expected Results

European Master

Scan Here

VET on RES

Scan Here

Read More on skillbill-project.eu

Accelerate RES deployment at several levels!

Ultimate goal!

Meet our tools

Step forward, break the ice, and together, let's unlock the potential of this incredible journey”

PARTNERS

Where did you travel first after Covid-19?

And also we will use miro

“Any question on the tools?”

Co-creation Workshop

Desired Outcomes - Goals

- Co-evaluate the operation of the Working Groups
- Understand the operation
- Design the future topics of discussion

Why to participate

- Ignite the Working Groups
- Co-evaluate the operational model
- Co-create tailored topic of discussion for the future, based on your interests

Co-creation workshop

Presentation of the Joint Initiative & Working Groups' Operation

Stakeholder Joint Initiative at a glance

Working Groups Goals and expected outcomes

Identification of new jobs and skills required

Translation of technological advantages into education / training needs

Solutions for driving the development and adoption of sustainable renewable energy and fuel techs

Directions for regulatory shift to shape a favorable environment for RES diffusion

Guidelines for education / training programmes to facilitate skilling, reskilling & upskilling

20 Policy Recommendations

Presentation of the Working Groups

PARTNERS

Working Groups... a definition

- collaborative teams
- specific objectives
- diverse skills, expertise,
and perspectives
- common goal

PARTNERS

What are the Working Groups under the framework of SKILLBILL?

- Interdisciplinary nature**
- Experts from quadruple helix**
- With different backgrounds**
- Unique perspective**
- Teamwork**
- Cooperation**
- Problem Solving**
- Leverage diverse skills**

SKILLBILL Working Groups Benefits

Professional Relations

Insights Knowledge Expansion

Collaboration and Networking

Skills Development Impact Influence

Synergies Problem Solving

Teamwork Remuneration

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Number and thematic focus of Working Groups (WG)

WGs in details

Initial Design- Operational Model

Sustainable and Renewable Electricity

Sustainable Mobility

AzzeroCO, Q-PLAN INTERNATIONAL, WHITE, UNIVERSITÀ TUSCIA, Metropolia University of Applied Sciences, Utrecht University, EREF, SINERGIE, PEDAL CONSULTING

Funded by the European Union

Number and thematic focus of Working Groups (WG)

WGs in details

Initial Design- Operational Model

Sustainable and Renewable Heat

Sustainable and Renewable Fuels

AzzeroCO, Q-PLAN INTERNATIONAL, WHITE, UNIVERSITÀ TUSCIA, Metropolia University of Applied Sciences, Utrecht University, EREF, SINERGIE, PEDAL CONSULTING

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How to get involved as an expert in the Working Groups?

Selection criteria

- Interest
- Availability
- Relevance Expertise
- Appropriateness
- Representativeness (Quadruple helix & each WG ideally gender-balanced)
- Willingness
- Gender

Monitoring Framework

- Number of members per WG (signed consent form)
- Number of meetings to be performed
- Number of attendees in each meeting
- Policy Recommendations developed

WGs Timeline & Effort

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“Raise your hand, ignite your curiosity, and let your questions fuel our workshop discussion!”

Bring

Ideas

Together

Based on the operation of the working groups presented, please indicate your level of satisfaction

Let us know your suggestions

Visit [Miro](#)

Session I: Suggestions of Improvements on Working Groups Operation

Wrap - up suggestions

PARTNERS

AzzeroCO, Q-PLAN INTERNATIONAL, WHITE, UNIVERSITÀ DELLA TUSCIA, Metropolia University of Applied Sciences, Utrecht University, EREF, SINERGIE, PEDAL CONSULTING

Smile wide and capture the spirit of our united energy!

PARTNERS

AzzeroCO, Q-PLAN INTERNATIONAL, WHITE, UNIVERSITÀ DELLA TUSCIA, Metropolia University of Applied Sciences, Utrecht University, EREF, SINERGIE, PEDAL CONSULTING

Family Photo

Meetings of the Working Groups

PARTNERS

Roles

Q-PLAN

- Communicate with initially engaged members
- Manage Personal Data for WGs (collect and store consent forms)
- Invite the Members to participate in the meetings
- Share feedback forms if needed
- Support the organisation of meetings (administrative role)

Lighthouse experts

- Chair the meeting
- Prepare questions, agenda and topic of the meeting 1 month prior
- Animate the exchange between meetings-warm up the team
- Complete a report after each meeting
- Lead the technology discussion (technical role)

Meetings of the WGs

1st meeting

When Nov 2023 ~1.5h

Platform MS Teams

4 WG separate meetings

Topic

Solutions for driving the development and adoption of RES techs

2nd meeting

When May 2024 ~1.5h

Platform MS Teams

4 WG separate meetings

Topic

Directions for regulatory shifts to shape favorable environment for RES diffusion

Meetings

3rd meeting

When Nov 2024 ~1.5h

Platform MS Teams

4 WG separate meetings

Topic

Guidelines for educational /training programs to facilitate skilling reskilling upskilling

Plenary

When May 2025 ~1.5h

Platform MS Teams

WG All WGs together

Topic

Identify new jobs and skills required
Translate technological advantages into educational/training needs

Members also invited to
2 Mobilisation & Mutual
Learning (MML) workshops

In Dec 2024 ~2-3h

In June 2025 ~2-3h

PARTNERS

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the European Union

WG Meetings

**What to expect
as a member ?**

- Receive Official Invitation**
[Accompanied by Terms of Reference, Informed Consent Form, Declaration of Acceptance]
- Officially Accept the Membership**
[for the Declaration and Informed Consent Form]
- Receive invitation and agenda**
[1 month prior each meeting]
- Actively participate to meetings**
[along with a chat for ad hoc comms]
- Participate in MMLs**
[if it falls under your interests]
- Ask for Remuneration**
[You have to participate all 4 meetings]
- Respond to feedback forms**
[and prioritise the recommendations]

PARTNERS

“Raise your hand, ignite your curiosity, and let your questions fuel our workshop discussion!”

Bring

Ideas

Together

Let us know the topics of your interest

Visit **Miro**

Result

Miro

Vote significant/impactful proposal (in each one of the thematic Focuses)

PARTNERS

Highlights and discussion

Register to Working Groups

Feedback Form

thank you

For support and active participation. We really appreciate your feedback and expertise! We are looking forward to shape the future together!

PARTNERS

The banner features a central circular logo with a stylized green leaf and a female symbol. Below the logo, the text reads "skillbill" in a bold, lowercase font, with "skill" in green and "bill" in yellow. Underneath, in smaller text, it says "SKILL TO BOOST INNOVATION & PROFESSIONAL FULFILMENT IN A SUSTAINABLE ECONOMY".

Below the logo, the contact information is displayed: "CONTACT US: info@skillbill-project.eu".

Four social media icons are arranged horizontally: Facebook, Twitter, LinkedIn, and YouTube. Each icon is followed by the text "@ SKILLBILL Project".

At the bottom left, there is a QR code and the website URL "www.skillbill-project.eu".

At the bottom right, there is a logo for the European Union with the text "Funded by the European Union".

Annex XIV: Social Media Posts

 SKILLBILL Project 382 followers
2mo •

🌟🚀 Exciting News! Join us for the SKILLBILL Project Co-Creation Workshop! 🌟🚀

📌 Calling all stakeholders! 📌 The SKILLBILL project is thrilled to announce ...see more

Are you a RES expert?

0:20

 You and 23 others 2 comments · 10 reposts

 Send

 SKILLBILL Project 382 followers
2mo •

 Exciting News! Only 6 Days Left for the SKILLBILL Co-Creation Workshop!

 The countdown has begun for the highly anticipated SKILLBILL Project ...see more

You and 9 others 2 reposts

 Send

Be the first to comment on this

 SKILLBILL Project 382 followers
2mo •

🌟🚀 Only 5 Days Left for the SKILLBILL Co-Creation Workshop! 🌟🚀

📌 The countdown continues for the SKILLBILL Project Co-Creation Works ...see more

0:09 Funded by the European Union

 You and 15 others 1 repost

 Send

Be the first to comment on this

 The countdown is still on!
 [...see more](#)

0:09 Supported by the European Union

 You and 15 others 4 reposts

 Send

Be the first to comment on this

The project

SKILLBILL's overall objective is to develop a large and strong foundation for the growth and acceleration of renewable energy's deployment, thanks to engaging with stakeholders of the whole chain, diffusing scientific culture and skilling multi-level workers. The basic idea underling the project is that the knowledge should be diffused at several different levels and qualitatively appropriate both to train the adequate number of workers and to increase RES awareness and to reach a more social and inclusive Europe. The project aims at creating several pathways to induce target groups to get interested or involved in RES besides their initial level of education and their working position. It's important, beside the creation of instruments for the upskilling and reskilling of workers, technician and designers, to have awareness modules for unspecific public in order to fight against lack of information, bad quality material, gender gap and the phenomenon of functional illiteracy: it is widely documented that lifelong suitable learning process is the fundamental driver to support the development, maintenance and update of skills. Thus, SKILLBILL proposes concrete actions to accelerate the deployment of renewable energy at different levels to analyse and involve all the interested parts in open discussion using adequate language; create several different pathways to increase skills after having mapped knowledge gap and without gender prejudice; develop and implement innovative learning method; and evaluate the work performed.

Coordinator: **AZZERO CO2 SRL (AzzeroCO2)**

PARTNER	SHORT NAME	
	AZZERO CO2 SRL	AzzeroCO2
	Q-PLAN INTERNATIONAL ADVISORS PC	Q-PLAN
	WHITE RESEARCH SPRL	WR
	UNIVERSITA DEGLI STUDI DELLA TUSCIA	UNITUS
	UNIVERSIDAD DE SEVILLA	USE
	METROPOLIA AMMATTIKORKEAKOULU OY	METROPOLIA
	UNIVERSITEIT UTRECHT	UU
	EUROPEAN RENEWABLE ENERGIES FEDERATION	EREF
	SINERGIE SOC CONS ARL	SINERGIE
	PEDAL CONSULTING SRO	PC

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